

Table 4. Appendix 1 to “Spectral magnetic helicity of solar active regions” by Gosain & Brandenburg

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2006	11	3	13:03	2.7	-0.3	-0.3	2.5	0	-0.04	5.41	-5.9	-5.4	29757	10921
2006	11	3	23:48	2.4	-0.1	-0.1	1.9	-3	-0.02	5.62	-5.9	1.1	29760	10921
2006	11	4	3:50	2.8	-2.1	-2.0	-2.2	-110	-0.28	5.56	-5.8	-1.3	29761	10921
2006	11	5	9:22	1.9	0.1	0.1	2.8	14	0.03	5.00	-6.3	19.7	29773	10921
2006	11	5	12:30	1.9	0.2	0.2	4.0	32	0.05	4.99	-6.2	21.5	29774	10921
2006	11	12	23:30	12.7	3.5	3.5	8.2	59	0.05	10.48	-3.8	-17.5	29808	10923
2006	11	13	10:00	12.9	3.5	3.5	1.2	7	0.05	10.14	-3.9	-13.5	29810	10923
2006	11	13	14:00	12.9	4.5	4.4	0.8	69	0.07	10.21	-3.9	-11.1	29811	10923
2006	11	13	21:30	12.8	3.7	3.7	5.6	51	0.06	10.41	-3.9	-6.8	29812	10923
2006	11	14	7:15	12.8	3.6	3.6	7.8	71	0.05	10.55	-3.9	-0.8	29813	10923
2006	11	14	16:30	12.3	2.5	2.5	5.2	28	0.04	10.68	-3.9	3.9	29814	10923
2006	11	15	11:10	10.7	0.2	0.2	4.5	12	0.00	10.40	-4.3	13.5	29816	10923
2006	11	15	15:21	10.7	-0.7	-0.6	-0.8	-21	-0.01	10.44	-4.3	15.9	29817	10923
2006	11	30	22:52	3.2	0.2	0.3	2.5	9	0.02	6.33	-8.6	-4.8	30083	10926
2006	12	3	6:20	2.9	-0.0	-0.1	2.3	4	-0.01	5.04	-8.6	25.4	30089	10926
2006	12	4	10:07	1.9	-0.0	-0.0	-0.1	-10	-0.01	5.12	-9.2	24.6	30092	10926
2006	12	9	10:00	10.8	-8.8	-8.8	-2.3	-202	-0.22	7.56	-5.7	-26.9	30107	10930
2006	12	9	11:20	11.0	-8.7	-8.7	-5.5	-179	-0.21	7.57	-5.7	-26.3	30108	10930
2006	12	9	12:40	11.1	-8.6	-8.5	2.7	-157	-0.20	7.64	-5.7	-25.5	30109	10930
2006	12	9	14:00	11.2	-8.0	-8.0	4.8	-140	-0.19	7.60	-5.7	-24.8	30110	10930
2006	12	9	17:10	11.3	-8.1	-8.1	10.7	-117	-0.19	7.61	-5.7	-23.0	30111	10930
2006	12	9	22:00	11.8	-8.1	-8.0	11.9	-128	-0.18	7.61	-5.7	-20.4	30112	10930
2006	12	10	1:00	12.1	-8.1	-8.0	4.9	-144	-0.17	7.62	-5.7	-18.7	30113	10930
2006	12	10	10:55	13.7	-8.2	-8.2	6.4	-197	-0.16	7.44	-5.7	-12.6	30114	10930
2006	12	10	21:00	14.4	-14.7	-14.5	-4.4	-489	-0.27	7.66	-5.7	-7.6	30115	10930
2006	12	11	3:10	15.2	-20.9	-20.7	-14.7	-720	-0.35	7.73	-5.7	-4.1	30116	10930
2006	12	11	8:00	15.5	-24.3	-24.0	-11.6	-806	-0.40	7.71	-5.7	-1.5	30117	10930
2006	12	11	11:10	15.6	-26.8	-26.6	-12.1	-802	-0.44	7.84	-5.7	0.4	30118	10930
2006	12	11	13:10	15.7	-28.3	-28.0	-10.6	-848	-0.46	7.81	-5.7	1.9	30119	10930
2006	12	11	17:00	16.2	-29.9	-29.7	-6.4	-850	-0.47	7.87	-5.7	3.5	30120	10930
2006	12	11	20:00	16.2	-30.7	-30.4	-10.8	-862	-0.48	7.86	-5.7	5.2	30121	10930

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2006	12	11	23:10	16.2	-32.4	-32.2	-12.7	-822	-0.50	7.92	-5.7	7.0	30122	10930
2006	12	12	3:50	16.7	-33.0	-32.8	-16.7	-892	-0.51	7.78	-5.7	9.6	30123	10930
2006	12	12	10:10	16.3	-33.0	-32.8	-19.2	-875	-0.52	7.80	-5.5	13.6	30124	10930
2006	12	12	15:30	15.8	-29.7	-29.5	-17.1	-781	-0.48	7.77	-5.7	16.0	30125	10930
2006	12	12	17:40	15.6	-28.1	-27.9	-17.5	-696	-0.46	7.81	-5.7	17.2	30126	10930
2006	12	12	20:30	15.0	-25.8	-25.7	-11.2	-596	-0.43	7.88	-5.7	18.8	30127	10930
2006	12	13	4:30	14.8	-29.1	-29.0	-14.1	-638	-0.49	7.91	-5.7	23.2	30128	10930
2006	12	13	7:50	14.2	-28.3	-28.2	-8.7	-618	-0.50	7.96	-5.7	25.1	30129	10930
2007	1	4	11:31	3.9	-1.8	-1.8	1.6	-23	-0.13	7.05	-3.8	-16.3	31208	10933
2007	1	4	18:40	3.9	-1.9	-1.9	-0.0	-35	-0.13	7.32	-3.8	-12.8	31209	10933
2007	1	5	0:57	4.2	-2.0	-2.0	3.9	-13	-0.13	7.19	-3.8	-9.3	31238	10933
2007	1	5	7:20	4.5	-2.1	-2.0	-1.5	-31	-0.13	7.19	-3.8	-5.8	31239	10933
2007	1	5	11:20	4.6	-2.0	-1.9	2.7	-34	-0.12	7.10	-3.8	-3.0	31240	10933
2007	1	6	10:12	4.0	-1.8	-1.7	-3.9	-47	-0.12	7.46	-5.3	8.7	31243	10933
2007	1	6	12:01	4.5	-1.7	-1.7	2.1	-13	-0.11	6.98	-5.3	10.3	31244	10933
2007	1	7	0:21	3.9	-1.6	-1.6	-1.2	-32	-0.11	7.21	-5.3	16.7	31245	10933
2007	1	7	12:00	3.8	-1.3	-1.3	3.5	-10	-0.10	6.89	-5.3	23.2	31246	10933
2007	1	7	18:45	3.9	-1.4	-1.4	0.1	-26	-0.10	6.89	-5.3	26.9	31247	10933
2007	1	31	19:02	7.5	-5.1	-5.1	4.0	-129	-0.20	6.63	-3.6	-15.1	31547	10940
2007	2	1	1:16	7.6	-5.3	-5.3	1.4	-104	-0.21	6.60	-3.6	-11.6	31548	10940
2007	2	1	7:42	7.6	-5.7	-5.7	0.7	-84	-0.23	6.54	-3.6	-8.0	31549	10940
2007	2	1	19:51	7.4	-6.0	-6.0	3.3	-93	-0.25	6.55	-3.6	-1.3	31551	10940
2007	2	2	1:50	7.3	-6.1	-6.1	-1.8	-88	-0.25	6.53	-3.6	2.0	31552	10940
2007	2	28	11:54	2.0	-0.3	-0.3	-0.2	0	-0.07	4.83	-5.7	-3.0	36464	10944
2007	2	28	17:57	1.5	-0.4	-0.4	-2.2	-25	-0.10	5.24	-5.7	0.2	36465	10944
2007	3	1	6:14	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	-1.5	0	-0.06	5.22	-5.7	7.1	36467	10944
2007	3	1	13:01	1.8	-0.4	-0.4	4.0	4	-0.08	4.75	-5.7	10.9	36469	10944
2007	3	1	19:10	1.4	-0.3	-0.3	0.4	1	-0.08	5.31	-5.7	14.2	36471	10944
2007	3	1	23:00	1.4	-0.3	-0.3	1.1	3	-0.07	5.31	-5.7	16.3	36472	10944
2007	3	2	0:15	1.4	-0.3	-0.3	-0.8	-3	-0.09	5.28	-5.7	17.0	36473	10944
2007	4	29	15:20	7.9	0.4	0.4	3.0	0	0.01	7.74	-9.5	-27.3	37349	10953
2007	4	29	20:00	8.0	-0.0	-0.0	-0.4	-35	-0.00	7.83	-9.5	-24.7	37350	10953
2007	4	30	4:51	8.3	0.1	0.1	7.1	-3	0.00	7.83	-9.5	-19.8	37352	10953

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2007	4	30	8:40	8.6	0.6	0.5	7.9	38	0.02	7.83	-9.5	-17.7	37353	10953
2007	4	30	12:30	8.7	0.9	0.8	9.0	34	0.03	7.94	-9.5	-16.2	37354	10953
2007	4	30	15:30	8.7	0.6	0.6	4.8	-2	0.02	7.88	-9.5	-14.6	37355	10953
2007	4	30	18:35	8.7	0.1	0.0	-0.3	-23	0.00	7.71	-9.5	-11.6	37356	10953
2007	4	30	22:30	8.8	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-2	-0.00	7.81	-9.5	-10.7	37357	10953
2007	5	1	1:50	8.7	-0.5	-0.5	-4.5	-43	-0.01	7.87	-9.5	-8.9	37358	10953
2007	5	1	5:00	8.5	-0.4	-0.5	3.7	-32	-0.01	7.87	-9.5	-7.1	37359	10953
2007	5	1	8:00	8.1	0.3	0.3	4.8	-7	0.01	7.93	-9.5	-5.4	37360	10953
2007	5	1	10:46	8.2	0.7	0.7	7.0	14	0.02	8.04	-9.5	-4.8	37361	10953
2007	5	1	14:00	7.9	0.9	0.9	5.4	0	0.03	8.19	-9.5	-3.3	37362	10953
2007	5	1	16:30	7.7	0.8	0.8	-4.3	-20	0.03	8.20	-9.5	-1.9	37363	10953
2007	5	1	19:30	7.6	1.2	1.2	1.5	5	0.04	8.07	-9.5	-0.3	37364	10953
2007	5	1	21:00	7.6	1.2	1.2	-0.8	16	0.04	8.05	-9.5	0.8	37365	10953
2007	5	2	0:15	7.0	1.3	1.3	2.5	30	0.05	8.16	-9.5	2.3	37366	10953
2007	5	2	4:00	6.9	1.1	1.1	3.5	18	0.04	8.10	-9.6	4.4	37367	10953
2007	5	2	7:00	6.7	1.4	1.4	1.4	24	0.05	8.13	-9.6	6.0	37368	10953
2007	5	2	10:00	6.8	1.6	1.6	3.5	45	0.06	8.01	-9.6	7.7	37369	10953
2007	5	2	11:15	6.9	1.7	1.7	6.7	61	0.07	7.61	-10.7	9.9	37370	10953
2007	5	2	14:00	6.8	2.2	2.1	7.2	58	0.08	7.77	-10.7	11.2	37371	10953
2007	5	2	17:30	6.9	2.7	2.7	2.0	45	0.10	7.70	-10.8	10.7	37372	10953
2007	5	2	20:10	6.6	2.8	2.8	-0.5	35	0.11	7.63	-10.7	14.6	37373	10953
2007	5	2	23:20	6.2	2.9	2.8	2.2	58	0.12	7.74	-10.7	16.3	37374	10953
2007	5	3	3:00	5.8	2.9	2.9	6.3	85	0.14	7.31	-10.7	18.3	37375	10953
2007	5	3	6:14	5.9	2.9	2.9	1.9	68	0.13	7.55	-10.7	20.1	37376	10953
2007	5	3	9:00	5.6	2.9	2.8	0.4	53	0.13	7.57	-10.7	21.6	37377	10953
2007	5	3	10:15	5.6	2.8	2.8	6.0	104	0.14	7.34	-10.4	23.2	37378	10953
2007	5	3	13:15	5.4	3.1	3.0	2.6	79	0.15	7.43	-10.4	24.6	37379	10953
2007	5	3	16:51	5.1	2.8	2.8	1.9	65	0.15	7.42	-10.4	26.6	37381	10953
2007	5	3	19:15	4.9	2.9	2.8	2.4	78	0.16	7.38	-10.4	27.9	37382	10953
2007	5	11	21:30	1.5	0.2	0.2	5.9	36	0.06	3.99	-9.3	4.9	37436	10955
2007	5	11	22:27	1.8	0.2	0.2	1.8	33	0.06	3.96	-9.3	5.8	37437	10955
2007	5	17	13:01	4.8	6.5	6.4	16.6	369	0.54	5.04	1.5	-26.9	37475	10956
2007	5	17	16:17	5.4	7.6	7.5	10.3	442	0.57	4.98	1.5	-25.3	37476	10956

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2007	5	17	18:18	5.4	8.1	8.0	19.7	492	0.59	5.04	1.5	-24.1	37477	10956
2007	5	18	3:46	5.3	8.3	8.1	17.1	496	0.60	5.17	1.5	-18.9	37481	10956
2007	5	18	6:06	5.0	8.1	7.9	14.4	405	0.61	5.30	1.5	-17.7	37482	10956
2007	5	18	8:43	5.0	8.1	7.9	16.7	430	0.61	5.26	1.5	-16.1	37484	10956
2007	5	19	4:35	4.1	5.4	5.3	7.5	217	0.53	4.93	1.5	-2.0	37488	10956
2007	5	19	7:42	4.0	4.2	4.2	2.7	70	0.47	4.59	1.5	-0.3	37489	10956
2007	5	20	6:41	3.5	5.0	4.9	11.3	282	0.57	5.07	1.5	12.5	37492	10956
2007	6	6	2:39	4.4	0.1	0.1	-4.4	3	0.01	4.45	-6.4	-23.3	38032	10960
2007	6	6	7:34	4.5	0.2	0.3	-1.1	6	0.02	4.39	-6.4	-20.5	38033	10960
2007	6	6	12:30	4.7	0.0	0.1	-0.3	10	0.00	4.40	-7.6	-18.0	38034	10960
2007	6	6	19:03	4.6	-0.0	0.0	1.4	0	-0.00	4.40	-7.6	-14.3	38035	10960
2007	6	7	16:32	3.9	-1.9	-1.9	-5.6	-66	-0.19	5.25	-7.6	-3.7	38038	10960
2007	6	8	12:17	3.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.4	3	-0.03	5.67	-8.9	6.6	38042	10960
2007	6	8	17:02	2.6	0.6	0.6	1.3	24	0.08	5.74	-8.8	8.2	38045	10960
2007	6	9	14:20	3.0	0.1	0.1	-2.0	11	0.02	4.31	-8.9	22.7	38050	10960
2007	6	29	18:51	3.0	-1.0	-1.0	1.3	-10	-0.12	5.82	-10.8	-25.2	38257	10961
2007	6	30	0:11	2.8	-1.0	-1.0	4.7	3	-0.11	5.97	-10.8	-23.1	38258	10961
2007	6	30	4:46	3.0	-0.9	-0.9	4.8	9	-0.11	5.80	-10.8	-19.8	38259	10961
2007	6	30	9:47	3.0	-0.9	-0.9	5.0	1	-0.09	6.04	-10.8	-17.1	38260	10961
2007	6	30	11:04	3.1	-0.9	-0.9	2.3	-7	-0.10	6.04	-10.8	-18.3	38261	10961
2007	6	30	16:04	3.2	-0.9	-0.9	1.6	-20	-0.09	6.07	-10.8	-14.8	38262	10961
2007	6	30	22:32	3.4	-0.9	-0.9	3.4	-7	-0.09	6.04	-10.8	-11.2	38263	10961
2007	7	1	3:32	3.4	-0.8	-0.8	1.2	-15	-0.08	6.09	-10.8	-8.4	38264	10961
2007	7	1	8:32	3.4	-0.7	-0.7	4.2	-7	-0.07	6.12	-10.8	-5.7	38265	10961
2007	7	1	13:32	3.1	-0.6	-0.6	4.0	11	-0.06	6.09	-10.8	-2.9	38266	10961
2007	7	1	20:20	3.0	-0.5	-0.5	0.0	-14	-0.06	6.07	-10.8	0.8	38267	10961
2007	7	2	7:21	2.8	-0.4	-0.4	3.3	0	-0.05	5.82	-10.8	6.9	38268	10961
2007	7	2	12:17	2.7	-0.5	-0.5	0.7	-3	-0.06	5.74	-10.8	9.6	38269	10961
2007	7	2	19:01	2.6	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3	-12	-0.06	5.63	-10.8	13.3	38273	10961
2007	7	3	3:03	2.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.2	-10	-0.04	5.67	-10.8	17.8	38274	10961
2007	7	3	11:30	2.1	-0.2	-0.2	-2.0	-17	-0.03	5.59	-10.8	22.4	38275	10961
2007	7	3	16:25	2.1	-0.1	-0.1	-1.9	-16	-0.02	5.53	-10.8	25.1	38276	10961
2007	7	12	0:27	4.8	-0.6	-0.7	3.6	6	-0.04	6.96	-6.7	-26.6	38334	10963

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2007	7	12	2:06	2.7	-0.7	-0.7	2.9	34	-0.09	5.63	-6.7	-25.7	38335	10963
2007	7	12	3:44	4.8	-0.9	-0.9	3.5	-4	-0.06	6.83	-6.7	-24.8	38336	10963
2007	7	12	7:02	3.0	-0.7	-0.8	16.5	163	-0.09	5.00	-6.7	-22.9	38337	10963
2007	7	12	8:40	4.8	-0.9	-0.9	2.4	-9	-0.05	6.75	-6.7	-22.1	38338	10963
2007	7	12	11:58	4.6	-1.0	-1.0	-1.3	-10	-0.06	6.79	-6.6	-19.3	38339	10963
2007	7	12	13:36	4.5	-0.9	-0.9	0.3	-4	-0.06	6.85	-6.7	-19.3	38340	10963
2007	7	12	15:15	4.7	-0.9	-0.9	-1.0	-11	-0.06	6.72	-6.7	-18.4	38341	10963
2007	7	12	17:00	2.7	-0.6	-0.6	3.3	28	-0.08	5.24	-6.7	-20.6	38342	10963
2007	7	12	18:34	4.7	-0.8	-0.7	-3.6	-32	-0.05	6.60	-6.7	-16.5	38343	10963
2007	7	13	1:05	4.7	-1.0	-1.0	5.1	0	-0.06	6.64	-6.7	-12.9	38344	10963
2007	7	13	2:45	4.7	-1.0	-1.0	-0.9	-41	-0.06	6.57	-6.7	-12.0	38345	10963
2007	7	13	4:24	4.7	-1.1	-1.1	-2.5	-37	-0.07	6.56	-6.7	-11.1	38346	10963
2007	7	13	7:43	4.3	-1.1	-1.1	0.4	-11	-0.08	6.50	-6.7	-9.2	38348	10963
2007	7	13	9:18	4.5	-1.1	-1.1	1.2	-30	-0.08	6.46	-6.7	-8.4	38349	10963
2007	7	13	12:33	4.2	-0.9	-0.8	8.9	0	-0.06	6.42	-6.7	-6.6	38350	10963
2007	7	13	19:07	3.9	-0.9	-0.9	5.4	5	-0.07	6.30	-6.7	-2.9	38351	10963
2007	7	14	1:41	4.0	-0.6	-0.6	6.1	-5	-0.05	6.11	-6.7	0.7	38352	10963
2007	7	14	21:23	3.7	-1.0	-1.0	-2.9	-27	-0.09	5.88	-6.7	12.2	38353	10963
2007	7	15	13:48	3.3	-0.9	-0.9	-2.1	-52	-0.09	5.98	-6.7	21.3	38354	10963
2007	7	16	11:08	2.6	-0.2	-0.2	-2.7	-26	-0.02	6.21	-6.3	23.8	38356	10963
2007	8	7	7:00	0.7	-0.1	-0.1	-0.4	-5	-0.08	3.00	-5.0	-28.2	38788	10966
2007	8	7	13:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-0.5	0	-0.05	2.95	-5.3	-25.0	38789	10966
2007	8	7	15:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.1	3	-0.07	2.89	-5.3	-24.0	38790	10966
2007	8	7	17:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.5	16	-0.05	2.82	-5.3	-22.8	38791	10966
2007	8	7	19:00	0.9	-0.1	-0.1	0.5	-3	-0.07	2.82	-5.3	-21.9	38792	10966
2007	8	7	21:00	0.9	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-4	-0.09	2.81	-5.3	-20.8	38793	10966
2007	8	9	2:55	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.9	4	-0.09	3.46	-5.2	-4.1	39195	10966
2007	8	9	4:33	1.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.4	-13	-0.09	3.41	-5.2	-3.2	39196	10966
2007	8	9	7:00	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	4.2	-4	-0.09	3.42	-5.2	-1.9	39197	10966
2007	8	9	23:00	0.9	-0.1	-0.1	1.0	-5	-0.09	3.45	-5.2	7.0	39732	10966
2007	8	25	11:00	1.9	-0.9	-0.9	-0.9	-45	-0.20	4.91	-5.6	-26.7	45193	10969
2007	8	25	12:00	1.9	-0.8	-0.8	-0.9	-39	-0.18	4.89	-5.6	-26.1	45194	10969
2007	8	25	13:00	1.9	-0.9	-0.8	0.3	-34	-0.19	4.93	-5.6	-25.6	45195	10969

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2007	8	25	14:00	1.9	-0.9	-0.9	-0.3	-42	-0.19	4.98	-5.6	-25.0	45196	10969
2007	8	25	15:00	1.8	-0.9	-0.9	-0.1	-40	-0.20	4.99	-5.6	-24.5	45197	10969
2007	8	27	7:34	1.9	-0.7	-0.7	6.2	-7	-0.14	5.23	-4.6	-2.6	45201	10969
2007	8	27	10:36	1.8	-0.6	-0.6	1.5	-16	-0.12	5.23	-4.5	-1.6	45202	10969
2007	8	27	13:00	1.7	-0.6	-0.6	2.8	-19	-0.15	5.10	-4.5	-0.1	45203	10969
2007	8	27	16:15	1.9	-0.8	-0.7	1.9	-23	-0.15	5.09	-4.5	1.5	45204	10969
2007	8	28	7:06	2.0	-0.8	-0.8	2.1	-28	-0.16	5.07	-4.5	9.8	45393	10969
2007	8	28	10:08	2.0	-0.7	-0.7	0.9	-17	-0.13	4.98	-4.2	10.8	45394	10969
2007	8	28	11:16	2.1	-0.7	-0.7	4.0	-3	-0.13	4.86	-4.1	11.7	45395	10969
2007	8	28	17:04	2.1	-0.8	-0.8	3.5	-2	-0.15	4.81	-4.1	14.7	45396	10969
2007	8	28	18:32	2.1	-0.7	-0.7	2.9	0	-0.15	4.79	-4.1	15.5	45397	10969
2007	8	28	20:08	2.0	-0.6	-0.6	4.0	9	-0.13	4.79	-4.1	16.4	45398	10969
2007	8	28	21:46	2.0	-0.6	-0.6	-1.7	-23	-0.13	4.73	-4.1	17.3	45399	10969
2007	8	28	23:21	2.0	-0.7	-0.7	-0.7	-31	-0.14	4.83	-4.1	18.1	45400	10969
2007	8	29	0:46	1.9	-0.6	-0.6	-3.5	-28	-0.13	4.81	-4.1	18.9	45401	10969
2007	8	29	2:20	1.9	-0.6	-0.6	-0.9	-14	-0.13	4.79	-4.1	19.8	45402	10969
2007	8	29	3:57	1.8	-0.7	-0.7	-1.7	-27	-0.15	4.87	-4.1	20.7	45403	10969
2007	8	29	7:12	1.7	-0.7	-0.7	-1.2	-30	-0.16	4.90	-4.1	22.5	45404	10969
2007	8	29	8:49	1.7	-0.6	-0.6	-2.4	-30	-0.16	4.91	-4.1	23.4	45405	10969
2007	9	29	12:40	0.9	0.0	0.0	1.0	-4	0.01	3.34	2.4	-0.3	45790	10971
2007	10	6	15:05	0.8	0.1	0.1	1.1	13	0.05	3.55	-5.1	0.1	45955	10972
2007	10	6	16:30	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.0	8	0.06	3.50	-5.1	0.9	45956	10972
2007	10	6	17:30	0.8	0.1	0.1	1.2	12	0.05	3.41	-5.1	1.4	45957	10972
2007	10	6	18:50	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.5	8	0.01	3.37	-5.1	2.1	45958	10972
2007	10	6	20:10	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.9	13	0.07	3.24	-5.1	2.9	45959	10972
2007	10	6	21:25	0.8	0.0	0.0	1.2	14	0.03	3.24	-5.1	3.6	45960	10972
2007	10	7	2:26	0.7	0.0	0.0	1.9	16	0.02	3.18	-5.1	6.4	45961	10972
2007	10	7	3:26	0.7	0.0	0.0	1.4	18	0.03	3.19	-5.1	6.9	45962	10972
2007	10	7	4:26	0.7	0.0	-0.0	0.2	11	0.00	3.14	-5.1	7.5	45963	10972
2007	10	7	5:26	0.6	-0.0	-0.0	0.6	14	-0.01	3.16	-5.1	8.0	45964	10972
2007	10	7	6:15	0.6	0.0	0.0	2.2	17	0.02	3.13	-5.1	8.5	45965	10972
2007	10	7	7:15	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.9	6	0.02	3.12	-5.1	9.0	45966	10972
2007	10	7	8:15	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.1	10	0.05	3.03	-5.1	9.6	45967	10972

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2007	10	7	9:15	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.2	10	0.02	2.96	-5.1	10.2	45968	10972
2007	10	7	10:58	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.2	15	0.02	2.95	-5.1	11.1	45969	10972
2007	10	7	11:58	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.6	15	0.03	2.99	-5.1	11.7	45970	10972
2007	10	7	12:58	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.2	1	0.01	2.95	-5.1	12.2	45971	10972
2007	10	7	13:58	0.5	-0.0	-0.0	-0.9	6	-0.01	2.94	-5.1	12.8	45972	10972
2007	12	9	11:41	3.4	0.1	0.1	0.5	-27	0.01	5.47	-7.8	-16.4	46556	10978
2007	12	10	6:20	3.0	0.9	0.9	4.0	38	0.11	5.40	-7.9	-23.6	46559	10978
2007	12	10	11:24	3.2	0.6	0.7	-0.3	-11	0.08	5.19	-7.9	-20.8	46560	10978
2007	12	10	11:54	3.1	0.7	0.7	-0.3	-11	0.08	5.29	-7.9	-20.6	46561	10978
2007	12	10	12:24	3.1	0.7	0.8	1.1	-15	0.09	5.27	-7.9	-20.3	46562	10978
2007	12	10	12:54	3.1	0.7	0.7	2.5	7	0.08	5.24	-7.9	-20.0	46563	10978
2007	12	10	13:24	3.1	0.7	0.8	1.4	-29	0.09	5.22	-7.9	-19.7	46564	10978
2007	12	10	13:54	3.1	0.7	0.7	0.4	-23	0.08	5.14	-7.9	-19.5	46565	10978
2007	12	10	14:24	3.2	0.4	0.5	1.6	-27	0.05	5.14	-7.9	-19.2	46566	10978
2007	12	10	14:54	3.1	0.6	0.6	-1.6	-30	0.08	5.12	-7.9	-18.9	46567	10978
2007	12	10	15:24	3.1	0.7	0.7	3.2	-13	0.08	5.01	-7.9	-18.6	46568	10978
2007	12	10	15:54	3.1	0.7	0.7	3.2	0	0.09	4.91	-7.9	-18.4	46569	10978
2007	12	11	6:34	2.9	0.7	0.7	-2.5	4	0.10	4.84	-7.9	-10.2	46570	10978
2007	12	11	7:04	2.9	0.7	0.7	-2.4	7	0.10	4.78	-7.9	-9.9	46571	10978
2007	12	13	2:56	6.7	-1.3	-1.3	3.3	-39	-0.06	6.72	-7.9	14.4	46580	10978
2007	12	13	9:24	6.8	-1.2	-1.1	-5.7	-87	-0.05	7.06	-7.9	17.9	46581	10978
2007	12	13	12:18	7.4	-1.8	-1.8	0.6	-24	-0.07	7.12	-7.9	19.8	46582	10978
2008	10	14	12:49	0.8	0.0	0.0	1.5	2	0.02	3.66	27.5	-7.2	49645	11005
2008	10	15	8:00	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.1	6	0.02	3.39	27.5	3.1	49646	11005
2008	10	15	12:54	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.0	5	0.03	3.29	27.5	5.8	49647	11005
2009	9	26	11:11	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.4	6	0.07	2.92	21.3	16.0	52591	11027
2009	12	27	23:10	1.7	0.5	0.4	6.6	77	0.13	4.21	-27.4	-30.3	53821	11039
2010	1	1	11:03	2.8	-0.1	-0.1	2.5	19	-0.02	5.73	-27.4	27.5	53827	11039
2010	1	24	13:00	2.8	-0.1	-0.1	8.9	100	-0.02	4.95	-25.3	-29.9	53943	11041
2010	1	24	16:05	2.7	-0.1	-0.2	7.6	94	-0.01	4.98	-25.3	-28.3	53944	11041
2010	1	25	0:01	2.4	-0.1	-0.2	10.8	97	-0.02	4.99	-25.3	-24.0	53946	11041
2010	1	25	3:40	2.2	-0.1	-0.1	9.4	106	-0.02	5.03	-25.3	-22.1	53947	11041
2010	1	25	9:30	2.1	0.0	-0.1	8.4	107	0.00	5.17	-25.3	-18.9	53948	11041

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2010	1	25	12:30	1.8	-0.0	-0.1	10.1	90	-0.01	5.10	-25.3	-17.4	53949	11041
2010	1	25	15:30	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	9.4	92	-0.02	5.26	-25.3	-15.7	53950	11041
2010	1	26	2:31	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	6.3	67	-0.02	5.15	-25.3	-9.8	53952	11041
2010	1	26	7:00	1.7	-0.2	-0.2	6.8	69	-0.04	5.23	-25.3	-7.5	53953	11041
2010	1	26	21:27	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	4.7	40	-0.02	3.78	-25.3	1.0	53954	11041
2010	1	27	5:05	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	3.0	32	-0.04	5.15	-25.3	4.4	53959	11041
2010	1	27	10:00	1.4	-0.3	-0.3	1.7	24	-0.09	5.04	-25.3	7.0	53960	11041
2010	1	27	15:00	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	2.3	20	-0.06	5.07	-25.3	9.7	53961	11041
2010	1	27	21:09	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	1.9	13	-0.06	5.04	-25.3	12.9	53962	11041
2010	1	28	3:20	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.8	12	-0.05	4.86	-25.3	16.2	53963	11041
2010	1	28	9:00	1.3	-0.1	-0.1	1.6	4	-0.02	4.63	-25.3	19.3	53964	11041
2010	1	28	10:41	0.9	0.1	0.1	-1.0	9	0.08	3.63	-25.3	20.4	53965	11041
2010	1	28	12:10	1.2	-0.0	-0.0	-1.1	-1	-0.00	3.36	-25.3	21.2	53966	11041
2010	1	28	13:40	1.3	-0.0	-0.0	-1.3	-6	-0.02	3.33	-25.3	22.0	53967	11041
2010	4	6	11:00	1.9	0.4	0.4	0.3	15	0.09	4.79	13.3	16.9	54193	11061
2010	4	6	14:00	1.8	0.5	0.5	1.5	32	0.12	4.69	13.3	18.6	54194	11061
2010	4	6	17:00	1.6	0.4	0.4	2.9	31	0.10	4.51	13.3	20.2	54195	11061
2010	4	6	18:50	1.7	0.3	0.3	1.4	23	0.08	4.63	13.3	21.2	54196	11061
2010	4	6	22:00	1.7	0.2	0.2	0.2	13	0.06	4.47	13.3	23.0	54197	11061
2010	4	7	1:00	1.6	0.2	0.2	1.1	19	0.06	4.39	13.3	24.7	54198	11061
2010	4	7	4:00	1.6	0.2	0.2	0.6	16	0.06	4.32	13.3	26.3	54199	11061
2010	4	7	7:00	1.6	0.2	0.2	1.1	13	0.07	4.28	13.3	28.0	54200	11061
2010	5	25	23:53	1.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-1	-0.06	5.07	-14.8	18.4	56734	11072
2010	6	19	21:30	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.2	6	0.06	2.93	26.0	-4.3	56781	11082
2010	6	19	23:05	0.4	0.0	0.0	2.9	13	0.05	2.67	26.0	-3.5	56782	11082
2010	6	20	0:41	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.6	23	0.05	2.52	26.0	-2.6	56783	11082
2010	6	20	2:19	0.7	0.1	0.1	4.0	40	0.15	2.59	26.0	-1.8	56784	11082
2010	6	20	4:00	0.9	0.2	0.1	3.5	65	0.15	2.63	26.0	-0.8	56785	11082
2010	6	20	9:00	1.1	0.2	0.2	2.3	49	0.14	3.06	26.0	1.9	56787	11082
2010	7	1	21:15	2.1	0.7	0.7	1.7	32	0.12	5.46	-21.1	-8.4	56811	11084
2010	7	1	23:55	2.2	0.7	0.8	2.0	33	0.12	5.61	-21.1	-7.0	56813	11084
2010	7	2	5:15	2.2	0.7	0.7	0.9	26	0.11	5.62	-21.1	-4.1	56814	11084
2010	7	2	13:15	2.3	0.7	0.7	1.5	29	0.12	5.55	-21.1	0.2	56815	11084

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2010	7	2	21:50	2.2	0.7	0.7	0.9	30	0.12	5.60	-21.1	4.9	56816	11084
2010	7	3	0:32	2.2	0.7	0.7	-0.0	30	0.12	5.58	-21.1	6.4	56818	11084
2010	7	4	14:50	1.6	0.4	0.4	1.0	20	0.08	5.52	-21.8	26.7	56841	11084
2010	7	4	16:20	1.6	0.3	0.3	0.3	17	0.08	5.51	-21.8	27.5	56842	11084
2010	7	4	18:14	1.6	0.4	0.4	0.2	20	0.09	5.47	-21.8	28.4	56843	11084
2010	7	4	19:51	1.5	0.3	0.3	0.5	16	0.08	5.54	-21.8	29.4	56844	11084
2010	7	4	21:26	1.5	0.3	0.3	0.5	17	0.08	5.54	-21.8	30.2	56845	11084
2010	7	13	6:50	2.0	-0.9	-0.9	-7.0	-91	-0.24	4.05	19.4	-27.4	56889	11087
2010	7	13	13:20	2.0	-0.6	-0.6	-2.9	-75	-0.16	4.05	19.4	-23.8	56890	11087
2010	7	13	23:30	2.2	-0.6	-0.5	-2.6	-86	-0.14	3.84	19.4	-18.2	56891	11087
2010	7	14	4:10	2.1	-0.6	-0.5	-4.7	-106	-0.16	3.74	19.4	-15.7	56892	11087
2010	7	14	22:17	1.8	-0.5	-0.4	0.1	-48	-0.13	3.82	19.4	-5.8	56894	11087
2010	7	15	8:01	1.7	-0.5	-0.4	4.1	-22	-0.14	3.97	19.4	-0.4	56897	11087
2010	7	15	12:55	2.2	-0.5	-0.5	4.3	-25	-0.11	4.19	19.4	2.4	56898	11087
2010	7	15	16:31	1.6	-0.5	-0.4	0.3	-35	-0.15	3.98	19.4	4.2	56899	11087
2010	7	15	23:00	1.5	-0.3	-0.3	0.8	-21	-0.11	3.86	19.4	7.8	56900	11087
2010	7	16	0:23	1.5	-0.3	-0.3	3.2	-16	-0.10	3.90	19.4	8.5	56901	11087
2010	7	16	2:02	1.5	-0.3	-0.3	4.8	-6	-0.10	3.96	19.4	9.4	56902	11087
2010	7	16	7:00	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	2.6	-8	-0.08	3.86	19.4	12.2	56904	11087
2010	7	16	8:36	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	3.3	-6	-0.08	3.81	19.4	13.0	56905	11087
2010	7	16	10:15	1.1	-0.1	-0.1	7.5	50	-0.07	3.13	19.4	14.1	56906	11087
2010	7	16	12:01	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	2.6	-4	-0.07	3.80	19.4	14.9	56907	11087
2010	7	16	13:35	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	4.1	-2	-0.10	3.81	19.4	15.8	56908	11087
2010	7	16	15:35	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	2.9	-2	-0.09	3.83	19.4	16.9	56909	11087
2010	7	16	18:35	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	4.4	1	-0.09	3.90	19.4	18.5	56910	11087
2010	7	16	20:30	1.2	-0.2	-0.2	5.7	0	-0.09	3.69	19.4	19.6	56911	11087
2010	7	16	22:00	1.2	-0.2	-0.2	3.9	-2	-0.10	3.71	19.4	20.4	56912	11087
2010	7	17	1:01	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	0.4	-2	-0.07	4.01	19.4	22.2	56913	11087
2010	7	17	4:18	1.1	-0.2	-0.2	2.4	3	-0.10	3.68	19.4	23.8	56914	11087
2010	8	1	20:30	4.8	-2.2	-2.2	-3.4	-71	-0.13	7.14	11.6	-21.4	57204	11092
2010	8	2	9:14	5.0	-2.0	-2.0	-1.6	-59	-0.11	7.09	11.6	-14.4	57205	11092
2010	8	2	21:00	5.2	-1.8	-1.8	0.1	-50	-0.10	7.06	11.6	-7.9	57208	11092
2010	8	3	15:00	4.8	-1.9	-1.9	-2.1	-62	-0.11	7.08	10.8	1.4	57211	11092

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2010	8	4	14:00	4.5	-1.6	-1.6	-0.0	-21	-0.10	7.03	10.8	14.2	57216	11092
2010	8	5	3:00	4.2	-1.0	-1.0	1.1	-32	-0.07	6.86	10.8	21.4	57217	11092
2010	8	5	11:09	4.0	-1.1	-1.1	0.4	-34	-0.08	6.72	10.9	25.3	57218	11092
2010	8	9	10:05	2.5	-0.4	-0.4	-1.0	-25	-0.06	5.94	9.6	-9.8	57688	11093
2010	8	9	19:05	2.5	-0.4	-0.4	1.0	-15	-0.06	5.94	9.6	-4.8	57689	11093
2010	8	9	22:05	2.4	-0.4	-0.4	0.3	-3	-0.06	5.92	9.6	-3.1	57690	11093
2010	8	10	6:15	2.3	-0.5	-0.4	1.6	-15	-0.06	6.10	9.6	1.4	57691	11093
2010	8	10	9:15	2.2	-0.5	-0.5	2.0	-12	-0.07	6.06	9.6	3.1	57693	11093
2010	8	11	3:30	1.9	-0.5	-0.5	0.6	-17	-0.09	5.97	9.6	13.2	57778	11093
2010	8	11	6:30	1.8	-0.6	-0.6	0.8	-16	-0.10	6.02	9.6	14.9	57779	11093
2010	8	12	22:30	0.5	-0.0	-0.0	0.3	-1	-0.03	3.11	13.2	-15.5	57947	11098
2010	8	30	2:18	2.1	-0.3	-0.3	1.4	-2	-0.05	5.95	12.4	-7.4	58040	11101
2010	8	30	17:05	2.3	-0.3	-0.3	2.2	-1	-0.05	5.74	12.4	0.8	58043	11101
2010	8	31	2:30	2.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.7	-5	-0.04	5.69	12.4	6.0	58044	11101
2010	9	16	16:30	1.0	-0.0	-0.1	4.1	38	-0.01	4.72	-19.9	-2.6	58142	11106
2010	9	18	10:15	1.1	0.1	0.1	-0.8	-4	0.04	4.79	-19.9	19.6	58148	11106
2010	9	26	7:20	1.8	0.5	0.5	-1.9	32	0.10	5.58	22.4	-30.5	58178	11109
2010	9	27	7:42	1.9	0.4	0.4	-0.5	16	0.07	5.51	22.4	-17.2	58182	11109
2010	9	28	12:05	5.4	-0.1	-0.1	3.7	10	-0.00	7.38	20.6	4.8	58188	11109
2010	10	13	18:20	0.9	0.1	0.1	3.4	11	0.05	4.44	-19.7	-15.4	58255	11112
2010	10	14	19:00	1.1	0.1	0.1	6.6	57	0.08	3.09	-19.7	-2.0	58256	11112
2010	10	15	6:15	1.3	0.1	0.1	4.3	42	0.06	3.02	-19.7	4.1	58257	11112
2010	10	15	11:15	1.3	0.1	0.1	6.0	41	0.06	3.14	-19.7	6.8	58258	11112
2010	10	15	12:30	1.2	0.1	0.1	5.9	42	0.07	3.16	-19.7	7.5	58259	11112
2010	10	15	13:45	1.2	0.2	0.1	5.4	50	0.09	3.13	-19.7	8.2	58260	11112
2010	10	15	15:00	1.3	0.2	0.1	3.6	44	0.09	3.14	-19.7	8.9	58261	11112
2010	10	18	18:32	2.2	-0.3	-0.3	-1.9	-38	-0.06	5.29	16.8	-12.5	58272	11113
2010	10	20	4:00	1.8	-0.4	-0.4	0.5	-15	-0.08	5.17	17.4	3.7	58273	11113
2010	10	20	12:01	1.6	-0.3	-0.3	-0.9	-18	-0.07	5.21	17.4	8.3	58274	11113
2010	10	20	21:30	1.6	-0.3	-0.2	0.7	-14	-0.06	5.11	17.4	13.3	58275	11113
2010	10	23	11:00	1.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0	0.00	4.48	23.0	-29.1	58304	11117
2010	10	24	8:30	2.5	0.3	0.3	-1.1	8	0.05	4.61	23.0	-17.4	58305	11117
2010	10	25	9:00	3.4	0.6	0.6	-0.7	78	0.08	4.74	23.0	-4.1	58307	11117

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2010	10	25	17:30	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-4	-0.02	4.92	23.0	0.6	58308	11117
2010	10	25	22:16	4.9	1.1	1.1	13.3	82	0.08	5.59	23.0	3.3	58310	11117
2010	10	26	10:45	6.3	0.9	0.9	6.5	68	0.05	6.32	21.0	6.5	58314	11117
2010	10	26	14:50	6.5	0.8	0.8	8.3	60	0.04	6.55	21.0	8.7	58315	11117
2010	10	27	2:00	7.4	-0.3	-0.3	0.4	13	-0.01	6.94	21.0	14.8	58320	11117
2010	10	27	6:50	7.5	-1.4	-1.4	2.6	-44	-0.05	7.10	21.0	17.4	58321	11117
2010	10	27	11:20	7.7	-1.6	-1.6	-5.1	-40	-0.06	7.17	21.0	19.9	58322	11117
2010	10	27	17:01	3.0	-0.8	-0.8	1.7	14	-0.09	5.94	21.0	22.4	58323	11117
2010	11	13	15:32	1.1	0.3	0.3	5.4	67	0.19	3.24	-22.7	17.5	58389	11123
2010	11	14	15:31	5.0	-0.5	-0.5	3.4	48	-0.03	5.48	12.7	11.7	58390	11124
2010	11	30	9:27	4.2	-0.9	-0.8	4.2	-21	-0.07	5.69	13.3	17.4	59320	11130
2010	11	30	11:31	3.9	-0.9	-0.8	2.2	-17	-0.08	5.55	13.3	18.6	59321	11130
2010	11	30	13:31	4.0	-1.0	-1.0	4.5	-14	-0.09	5.77	13.3	19.7	59322	11130
2010	11	30	15:31	3.9	-0.9	-0.9	6.5	-5	-0.08	5.75	13.3	20.8	59323	11130
2010	11	30	17:31	4.0	-1.1	-1.1	5.4	-21	-0.10	5.83	13.3	21.9	59324	11130
2010	11	30	20:01	4.0	-1.1	-1.1	6.8	-14	-0.09	5.82	13.3	23.3	59325	11130
2010	11	30	22:01	4.2	-1.2	-1.2	5.4	-26	-0.10	5.90	13.3	24.4	59326	11130
2010	12	1	0:31	4.1	-1.2	-1.2	5.2	-9	-0.10	5.98	13.3	25.8	59327	11130
2010	12	1	3:01	4.0	-1.2	-1.2	0.9	-26	-0.10	5.91	13.3	27.1	59328	11130
2011	1	22	9:31	2.3	-0.1	-0.1	1.3	17	-0.02	5.00	21.2	10.2	59441	11147
2011	1	22	11:31	3.5	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-26	-0.02	4.73	21.2	11.3	59442	11147
2011	1	22	13:31	3.7	0.4	0.3	4.3	127	0.05	4.66	21.2	12.3	59443	11147
2011	1	22	15:11	3.8	0.2	0.1	1.7	130	0.03	4.62	21.2	13.3	59444	11147
2011	1	22	18:31	3.6	0.0	0.0	-2.9	-2	0.00	4.76	21.2	15.1	59445	11147
2011	1	22	21:41	3.7	-0.1	-0.2	0.5	26	-0.01	4.71	21.2	16.8	59446	11147
2011	1	23	0:39	3.7	-0.1	-0.1	1.5	27	-0.01	4.84	21.2	18.4	59447	11147
2011	1	23	3:52	3.7	-0.1	-0.1	-0.9	11	-0.01	4.84	21.2	20.2	59448	11147
2011	1	23	9:01	3.8	-0.2	-0.1	1.6	-6	-0.02	4.94	21.2	23.0	59449	11147
2011	1	23	12:01	4.0	-0.1	-0.1	1.6	-4	-0.01	4.93	21.2	24.6	59450	11147
2011	1	23	15:01	3.9	0.0	0.0	1.7	17	0.00	4.94	21.2	26.3	59451	11147
2011	1	23	21:01	3.8	0.1	0.1	-1.6	3	0.01	4.93	21.2	29.6	59452	11147
2011	2	1	1:25	1.2	0.2	0.1	3.0	25	0.07	3.82	-19.9	-29.2	59471	11150
2011	2	1	4:40	1.2	0.2	0.2	3.2	38	0.09	3.75	-19.9	-27.4	59472	11150

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	2	1	8:00	1.1	0.2	0.1	5.8	43	0.08	3.55	-19.9	-25.6	59473	11150
2011	2	2	0:19	2.2	0.7	0.6	11.3	76	0.13	4.58	-20.4	-12.2	59474	11150
2011	2	2	2:00	2.1	0.6	0.6	10.8	67	0.12	4.61	-20.4	-11.3	59475	11150
2011	2	2	3:35	2.0	0.4	0.4	12.2	69	0.10	4.43	-20.4	-10.5	59476	11150
2011	2	2	5:15	2.0	0.4	0.4	5.0	46	0.10	4.39	-20.4	-9.6	59477	11150
2011	2	2	8:35	1.8	0.3	0.3	10.4	68	0.08	4.28	-20.4	-7.8	59479	11150
2011	2	3	2:35	1.5	0.1	0.1	7.0	29	0.05	3.58	-21.0	1.6	59498	11150
2011	2	12	10:00	1.8	0.2	0.2	5.4	63	0.06	3.47	-19.9	-22.7	59540	11158
2011	2	12	11:30	1.8	0.1	0.1	3.6	62	0.04	3.53	-20.2	-11.2	59541	11158
2011	2	12	13:00	1.8	0.1	0.1	2.7	35	0.04	3.55	-19.9	-21.1	59542	11158
2011	2	12	17:00	2.1	0.2	0.2	-2.0	11	0.05	3.58	-19.9	-18.9	59544	11158
2011	2	12	18:35	2.3	0.1	0.1	-3.6	-7	0.03	3.57	-19.9	-18.0	59545	11158
2011	2	12	20:00	2.5	0.1	0.1	4.5	39	0.03	3.61	-19.9	-17.3	59546	11158
2011	2	12	22:00	2.6	0.2	0.2	1.3	77	0.05	3.67	-19.9	-16.2	59547	11158
2011	2	13	1:00	3.4	0.8	0.8	5.3	153	0.13	3.68	-19.9	-14.5	59548	11158
2011	2	13	2:30	3.9	1.3	1.2	17.8	212	0.18	3.75	-19.9	-13.7	59549	11158
2011	2	13	4:00	4.2	1.4	1.2	16.7	247	0.17	3.94	-19.9	-12.9	59550	11158
2011	2	13	7:30	5.1	1.4	1.3	14.4	198	0.12	4.33	-19.9	-11.0	59551	11158
2011	2	13	9:20	5.9	1.4	1.3	14.3	217	0.10	4.46	-19.9	-10.0	59552	11158
2011	2	13	12:00	7.2	2.1	1.9	14.8	362	0.13	4.51	-19.9	-7.9	59553	11158
2011	2	13	16:00	8.4	2.5	2.2	15.2	419	0.13	4.60	-19.9	-6.4	59554	11158
2011	2	13	19:00	8.8	3.2	2.9	11.6	494	0.16	4.61	-19.9	-4.8	59555	11158
2011	2	13	21:30	9.0	3.1	2.7	18.7	601	0.15	4.65	-19.9	-3.4	59556	11158
2011	2	14	0:00	8.5	3.4	3.0	26.0	693	0.18	4.57	-19.9	-2.1	59557	11158
2011	2	14	6:30	8.5	2.7	2.4	35.4	590	0.13	4.74	-19.9	1.5	59559	11158
2011	2	15	10:11	6.7	4.1	3.9	15.7	440	0.26	4.69	-19.9	16.5	59560	11158
2011	2	15	12:11	6.5	4.5	4.2	18.1	445	0.28	4.78	-19.9	17.6	59561	11158
2011	2	15	14:11	6.6	4.0	3.8	18.2	425	0.25	4.75	-19.9	18.7	59562	11158
2011	2	15	15:40	6.8	4.5	4.2	20.4	519	0.28	4.71	-19.9	19.5	59563	11158
2011	2	15	18:40	6.5	4.4	4.2	17.0	464	0.28	4.75	-19.9	21.1	59564	11158
2011	2	15	20:40	6.3	4.9	4.8	8.5	391	0.31	4.94	-19.9	22.2	59565	11158
2011	2	15	23:30	6.1	5.2	5.1	5.0	311	0.33	5.06	-20.2	16.3	59566	11158
2011	2	16	1:00	5.7	5.5	5.4	10.3	365	0.38	5.10	-19.9	24.6	59567	11158

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	2	16	2:30	5.8	1.5	1.4	11.1	226	0.10	5.09	-19.9	25.4	59568	11158
2011	2	16	4:30	6.4	2.5	2.3	8.6	327	0.15	5.06	-19.9	26.5	59569	11158
2011	2	16	7:30	6.3	3.0	2.9	4.5	233	0.18	5.17	-19.9	28.3	59570	11158
2011	2	16	9:20	6.2	2.9	2.9	1.9	197	0.18	5.17	-19.9	29.1	59571	11158
2011	2	19	10:34	3.5	-0.8	-0.8	11.5	-61	-0.12	4.07	18.5	10.6	59583	11162
2011	2	19	14:20	3.3	-0.7	-0.7	9.7	9	-0.10	4.17	18.5	12.7	59584	11162
2011	2	19	18:17	3.0	-0.3	-0.3	3.2	0	-0.05	4.26	18.5	14.9	59585	11162
2011	2	20	0:02	2.8	0.1	0.0	4.5	59	0.01	4.75	18.5	18.0	59586	11162
2011	2	20	6:27	2.8	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	-34	-0.05	4.44	18.5	21.6	59587	11162
2011	2	20	12:00	2.8	-0.5	-0.5	2.3	-49	-0.08	4.53	18.5	24.6	59588	11162
2011	2	20	18:37	2.6	-0.5	-0.5	3.3	-26	-0.08	4.65	18.5	28.2	59589	11162
2011	3	10	9:41	7.7	-3.6	-3.5	-0.8	-125	-0.16	5.83	8.5	15.8	59690	11166
2011	3	10	14:40	6.9	6.0	5.8	15.8	322	0.32	5.44	8.5	18.6	59691	11166
2011	3	10	22:55	11.0	-0.3	-0.5	44.5	463	-0.01	5.56	8.5	23.2	59692	11166
2011	3	18	15:00	1.1	-0.0	0.0	-4.5	-26	-0.01	2.65	14.0	9.1	107956	11175
2011	3	18	19:45	2.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.6	-21	-0.05	3.42	14.0	11.8	107957	11175
2011	3	18	21:34	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	5.0	14	-0.02	3.56	14.0	14.1	107958	11175
2011	3	19	3:35	2.1	-0.1	-0.1	4.2	3	-0.03	3.71	14.0	16.1	107959	11175
2011	3	19	10:00	2.4	-0.1	-0.0	3.6	-11	-0.01	4.15	14.0	19.6	107960	11175
2011	3	27	23:52	3.2	2.5	2.5	7.0	83	0.30	5.24	-16.6	-4.9	107972	11176
2011	3	28	12:00	3.0	2.2	2.1	10.8	145	0.29	4.95	-16.6	1.8	107973	11176
2011	3	29	0:02	2.8	1.8	1.8	6.3	93	0.28	4.70	-16.6	8.3	107974	11176
2011	3	29	12:00	2.8	1.6	1.5	12.8	125	0.24	4.58	-16.6	14.9	107975	11176
2011	3	29	21:36	2.6	1.5	1.4	2.3	95	0.23	4.83	-16.6	20.1	107976	11176
2011	3	29	23:36	3.0	1.9	1.9	2.9	83	0.24	5.32	-18.4	17.9	107977	11176
2011	3	30	3:50	3.0	1.8	1.7	2.9	97	0.24	4.83	-18.4	20.2	107978	11176
2011	3	30	8:40	3.2	2.3	2.2	6.5	152	0.28	4.95	-18.4	22.9	107979	11176
2011	3	30	14:00	3.1	2.2	2.1	6.7	158	0.27	5.27	-18.4	25.8	107980	11176
2011	3	30	19:00	2.9	2.1	2.0	3.4	128	0.27	5.36	-18.4	28.5	107981	11176
2011	4	12	3:40	2.5	-0.5	-0.4	2.2	-32	-0.07	5.05	14.0	-26.8	108022	11190
2011	4	18	10:53	3.6	0.4	0.4	5.7	38	0.04	5.76	17.5	-11.0	108030	11193
2011	4	18	16:30	3.8	0.4	0.4	6.8	23	0.04	5.80	17.5	-7.9	108031	11193
2011	4	18	18:10	4.1	0.6	0.6	4.6	33	0.05	5.65	17.5	-7.0	108032	11193

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	4	18	23:00	4.2	1.2	1.2	8.2	45	0.10	5.69	17.5	-4.3	108033	11193
2011	4	24	3:15	5.3	2.9	2.7	13.2	250	0.22	4.99	-16.7	-14.1	108041	11195
2011	5	5	14:55	0.9	-0.2	-0.2	4.9	27	-0.14	3.64	16.9	2.2	108098	11203
2011	5	5	16:41	2.1	0.5	0.4	5.9	74	0.08	5.34	16.9	3.2	108099	11203
2011	5	5	23:07	1.9	-0.9	-1.0	5.2	3	-0.17	5.83	16.9	6.5	108103	11203
2011	5	6	0:43	1.8	-1.0	-1.0	3.8	-2	-0.18	5.93	16.9	7.9	108104	11203
2011	5	6	1:26	2.1	0.4	0.4	4.0	31	0.07	5.35	16.9	8.9	108105	11203
2011	5	6	3:50	1.9	-1.1	-1.1	6.3	-13	-0.21	5.96	16.9	9.3	108106	11203
2011	5	6	9:01	2.0	-1.4	-1.4	0.6	-45	-0.23	5.91	16.9	12.2	108108	11203
2011	5	6	15:35	3.3	-2.0	-1.9	5.0	-49	-0.19	6.06	16.0	9.5	108109	11203
2011	5	7	17:56	2.3	-1.8	-1.8	1.6	-41	-0.31	4.89	16.0	22.7	108110	11203
2011	5	7	21:12	2.5	-1.7	-1.7	1.7	-43	-0.26	5.04	16.0	24.5	108111	11203
2011	5	8	0:34	2.3	-1.4	-1.4	1.8	-15	-0.24	5.10	16.0	26.4	108112	11203
2011	5	8	3:40	2.7	-1.6	-1.5	3.8	-17	-0.21	5.50	16.0	28.1	108113	11203
2011	5	10	13:00	2.1	-0.1	-0.2	2.1	20	-0.05	3.16	20.4	-0.2	108125	11210
2011	5	10	18:20	2.0	-0.1	-0.1	5.5	38	-0.04	3.20	20.4	2.6	108126	11210
2011	5	11	0:40	1.9	-0.0	-0.0	6.8	39	-0.01	3.07	20.4	6.0	108127	11210
2011	5	11	12:15	1.5	0.0	0.0	9.5	49	0.01	3.00	20.4	12.4	108128	11210
2011	5	12	1:20	1.3	-0.0	-0.0	4.1	21	-0.02	2.85	20.4	19.5	108129	11210
2011	5	18	4:50	1.8	0.2	0.2	2.4	39	0.04	4.96	-26.2	29.7	108149	11214
2011	5	21	1:57	1.4	0.4	0.4	2.2	45	0.13	4.73	-17.4	-15.2	108157	11216
2011	5	21	3:35	1.4	0.4	0.4	1.4	39	0.11	4.73	-17.4	-14.3	108158	11216
2011	5	22	0:46	1.5	0.4	0.4	0.5	36	0.11	4.85	-17.2	-1.9	108160	11216
2011	5	22	4:03	1.6	0.4	0.3	2.4	36	0.10	4.71	-17.2	-0.2	108161	11216
2011	5	22	5:41	1.6	0.3	0.3	-0.5	29	0.08	4.79	-17.2	0.7	108162	11216
2011	5	22	7:20	1.5	0.3	0.3	1.0	34	0.08	4.78	-17.2	1.6	108163	11216
2011	5	22	8:58	1.5	0.4	0.4	0.2	34	0.10	4.86	-17.2	2.5	108164	11216
2011	5	22	10:37	1.5	0.4	0.4	2.5	39	0.10	4.89	-17.2	3.4	108165	11216
2011	6	1	15:11	4.5	2.4	2.4	5.2	80	0.19	5.70	-23.1	-21.9	108191	11226
2011	6	4	10:43	3.0	1.6	1.6	8.2	47	0.18	5.82	-23.1	12.4	108212	11226
2011	6	7	17:18	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.1	-6	-0.07	4.05	7.6	2.0	108220	11232
2011	6	7	20:33	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	-1.1	-11	-0.07	4.02	7.6	3.8	108221	11232
2011	6	8	0:15	1.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-6	-0.06	4.01	7.6	5.2	108222	11232

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	6	14	10:16	1.7	-0.1	-0.1	3.4	23	-0.02	4.68	-18.5	2.4	108358	11234
2011	6	14	11:46	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	2.3	5	-0.03	4.74	-18.5	3.2	108359	11234
2011	6	14	13:25	1.9	-0.2	-0.2	6.0	12	-0.04	4.79	-18.5	4.1	108360	11234
2011	6	14	15:04	2.0	-0.2	-0.2	3.6	-1	-0.04	4.89	-18.5	5.0	108361	11234
2011	6	14	16:51	2.0	-0.2	-0.2	5.0	17	-0.05	4.95	-18.5	6.0	108362	11234
2011	6	14	18:28	2.0	-0.2	-0.2	7.9	19	-0.05	4.98	-18.5	6.8	108363	11234
2011	6	15	6:16	2.1	-0.3	-0.3	2.7	-7	-0.07	4.95	-18.5	13.2	108365	11234
2011	6	15	14:26	3.2	-1.0	-1.0	5.3	-13	-0.11	5.60	-18.5	17.0	108368	11234
2011	6	15	15:53	3.3	-1.2	-1.2	12.1	18	-0.13	5.59	-18.5	18.5	108369	11234
2011	6	15	17:28	3.5	-1.2	-1.2	14.7	6	-0.12	5.56	-18.5	19.4	108370	11234
2011	6	15	19:05	3.7	-1.6	-1.6	8.7	-18	-0.15	5.63	-18.5	20.2	108371	11234
2011	6	15	20:42	3.9	-1.8	-1.8	10.0	-19	-0.16	5.71	-18.5	21.1	108372	11234
2011	6	15	22:18	4.0	-1.8	-1.8	7.8	3	-0.15	5.74	-18.5	22.0	108373	11234
2011	6	15	23:53	4.0	-1.9	-1.8	6.2	-2	-0.16	5.86	-18.5	22.9	108374	11234
2011	7	1	14:06	3.2	-1.1	-1.1	0.9	-12	-0.12	5.84	14.5	-28.9	108439	11243
2011	7	1	17:25	3.2	-1.1	-1.1	0.4	-17	-0.11	6.10	14.5	-27.9	108440	11243
2011	7	1	20:48	3.2	-1.0	-0.9	1.4	-14	-0.10	6.12	14.5	-26.6	108441	11243
2011	7	2	3:14	3.4	-0.9	-0.9	-3.0	-40	-0.08	6.29	14.5	-21.7	108443	11243
2011	7	2	6:32	3.3	-0.6	-0.6	-0.9	-6	-0.06	6.19	14.5	-20.1	108444	11243
2011	7	3	3:52	2.7	-0.7	-0.7	1.7	-14	-0.11	5.03	14.5	-8.0	108445	11243
2011	7	3	8:45	2.5	-0.7	-0.7	2.0	-7	-0.11	4.84	14.5	-5.0	108446	11243
2011	7	3	17:12	2.1	-0.6	-0.6	3.2	9	-0.12	4.79	14.5	-0.3	108450	11243
2011	7	3	20:15	2.5	-0.7	-0.7	2.5	-2	-0.11	5.04	14.5	1.4	108451	11243
2011	7	4	1:15	2.5	-0.7	-0.7	2.6	5	-0.11	5.03	14.5	4.1	108452	11243
2011	7	4	4:30	2.4	-0.7	-0.7	3.3	-21	-0.12	4.77	14.5	5.9	108453	11243
2011	7	4	7:55	2.3	-0.6	-0.6	2.7	-22	-0.12	4.70	14.5	7.8	108454	11243
2011	7	4	16:12	2.2	-0.5	-0.5	1.2	-14	-0.11	4.44	14.5	12.4	108458	11243
2011	7	4	21:05	2.2	-0.6	-0.6	1.2	-15	-0.13	4.48	14.5	15.1	108459	11243
2011	7	5	0:15	2.1	-0.7	-0.7	2.2	-8	-0.15	4.46	14.5	16.8	108460	11243
2011	7	5	3:34	2.1	-0.7	-0.7	2.2	-11	-0.15	4.43	14.5	19.4	108461	11243
2011	7	5	6:55	2.1	-0.6	-0.6	4.3	-2	-0.14	4.55	14.5	20.5	108462	11243
2011	7	18	14:51	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	2.0	2	-0.05	3.33	7.2	0.1	108508	11256
2011	7	18	16:35	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.8	0	0.00	3.29	7.2	1.1	108509	11256

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	7	22	8:58	2.0	-0.6	-0.6	-0.1	-10	-0.10	5.29	22.5	-25.5	108528	11259
2011	7	22	10:36	1.9	-0.5	-0.5	1.1	0	-0.10	5.22	22.5	-24.6	108529	11259
2011	7	23	8:20	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	-2.0	15	-0.03	4.70	22.5	-12.8	108533	11259
2011	7	23	9:35	1.5	-0.1	-0.1	2.3	23	-0.03	4.61	22.5	-12.1	108534	11259
2011	7	23	11:13	1.5	-0.0	-0.1	2.3	17	-0.01	4.53	22.5	-11.2	108535	11259
2011	7	28	12:40	4.0	-2.8	-2.6	10.5	-91	-0.27	5.06	17.5	-25.0	108555	11260
2011	7	28	14:23	4.3	-2.7	-2.5	5.3	-120	-0.25	4.98	17.5	-24.1	108556	11260
2011	7	30	0:46	3.0	-0.7	-0.7	1.4	9	-0.11	4.59	17.5	-5.2	108561	11260
2011	7	30	10:39	5.1	-1.4	-1.4	0.2	-49	-0.07	7.47	17.7	2.6	108562	11260
2011	7	30	12:14	6.1	0.5	0.5	7.1	32	0.02	6.22	17.7	3.4	108563	11260
2011	7	30	14:05	4.7	-1.2	-1.2	1.4	-44	-0.07	7.34	17.7	4.5	108564	11260
2011	8	2	11:24	11.8	11.3	11.0	6.5	380	0.25	7.61	16.1	-9.2	108571	11263
2011	8	3	11:36	11.0	10.6	10.3	17.8	408	0.26	7.49	16.0	-2.6	108592	11263
2011	8	3	13:03	10.8	10.5	10.3	22.5	390	0.26	7.60	16.0	-1.8	108593	11263
2011	8	3	14:41	11.0	10.4	10.2	17.0	385	0.25	7.61	16.0	-0.9	108594	11263
2011	8	3	16:36	11.0	9.9	9.8	23.6	377	0.24	7.59	16.0	0.1	108595	11263
2011	8	3	18:28	10.8	10.1	10.0	18.2	357	0.24	7.65	16.0	1.1	108596	11263
2011	8	3	19:50	10.7	10.6	10.4	14.9	360	0.26	7.45	16.0	1.9	108597	11263
2011	8	3	21:27	10.6	10.5	10.4	11.3	369	0.26	7.63	16.0	2.8	108598	11263
2011	8	3	23:02	10.4	10.5	10.4	14.9	366	0.27	7.54	16.0	3.7	108599	11263
2011	8	4	2:10	10.6	11.0	10.8	14.5	402	0.28	7.40	16.0	5.4	108601	11263
2011	8	4	3:49	10.7	10.7	10.6	18.5	425	0.27	7.46	16.0	6.3	108602	11263
2011	8	4	7:06	10.8	11.2	11.0	17.7	446	0.28	7.42	16.0	8.1	108603	11263
2011	8	4	8:44	10.8	11.3	11.1	14.0	443	0.28	7.42	16.0	9.0	108604	11263
2011	8	4	15:37	10.2	10.2	10.1	19.7	368	0.27	7.36	16.0	12.8	108605	11263
2011	8	4	17:13	10.2	10.2	10.1	11.7	340	0.27	7.33	16.0	13.4	108606	11263
2011	8	23	11:14	6.3	-3.3	-3.3	-0.8	-75	-0.16	6.37	15.1	20.5	108681	11271
2011	8	23	17:30	4.8	-1.6	-1.6	-14.4	-145	-0.11	5.93	14.4	23.0	108682	11271
2011	8	29	7:34	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.6	-1	0.02	4.13	17.1	-21.8	108699	11277
2011	8	29	9:47	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	-3	0.01	4.17	17.1	-20.5	108701	11277
2011	8	29	21:12	2.0	0.8	0.7	0.2	30	0.14	5.27	14.7	-21.6	108703	11279
2011	8	30	7:35	1.2	0.0	0.0	1.6	4	0.01	3.96	17.0	-9.3	108704	11277
2011	8	30	9:40	1.1	-0.0	0.0	1.6	2	-0.00	4.06	17.2	-7.8	108706	11277

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	8	31	7:34	1.0	0.0	0.0	-0.5	-1	0.02	4.23	17.2	4.3	108708	11277
2011	8	31	9:45	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	2	0.00	4.14	17.2	5.5	108710	11277
2011	9	1	7:46	0.9	-0.0	-0.0	-0.3	2	-0.01	3.80	17.2	17.4	108712	11277
2011	9	1	10:14	1.0	-0.0	-0.0	-1.2	-11	-0.01	3.55	17.9	18.1	108714	11277
2011	9	1	10:44	3.7	2.1	2.1	0.9	44	0.22	5.15	-21.1	-23.4	108715	11281
2011	9	1	15:30	3.7	1.9	1.8	3.6	53	0.20	5.04	-21.1	-20.8	108716	11281
2011	9	7	5:00	4.7	2.7	2.5	8.5	218	0.23	4.94	13.3	21.2	108762	11283
2011	9	13	10:34	8.5	-8.0	-8.0	2.5	-134	-0.23	8.13	22.6	6.6	108779	11289
2011	9	13	12:04	8.4	-8.0	-8.0	-1.5	-162	-0.23	8.13	22.6	7.4	108780	11289
2011	9	13	15:46	8.6	-8.1	-8.0	2.1	-149	-0.23	8.06	31.4	8.3	108782	11289
2011	9	14	11:47	9.1	-8.1	-8.1	6.6	-153	-0.23	7.72	22.6	20.3	108783	11289
2011	9	14	13:15	9.1	-8.2	-8.2	7.5	-150	-0.23	7.74	22.6	21.1	108784	11289
2011	9	14	14:45	8.7	-6.9	-6.9	11.6	-116	-0.21	7.61	22.6	21.9	108785	11289
2011	9	14	16:20	8.8	-7.5	-7.5	10.8	-144	-0.22	7.65	22.6	22.8	108786	11289
2011	9	17	3:14	4.3	1.2	1.2	5.8	63	0.11	5.03	20.8	-16.8	108796	11295
2011	9	17	4:53	4.3	1.1	1.1	10.5	78	0.10	5.05	20.8	-15.4	108797	11295
2011	9	17	7:51	4.0	1.0	1.1	2.8	11	0.10	5.19	20.8	-15.0	108799	11295
2011	9	17	12:35	4.6	1.6	1.6	2.7	49	0.13	5.13	20.8	-11.7	108801	11295
2011	9	17	13:50	4.5	1.5	1.4	2.8	36	0.12	5.18	20.8	-11.0	108802	11295
2011	9	17	15:28	4.6	1.6	1.6	3.4	57	0.13	5.18	20.8	-10.1	108803	11295
2011	9	17	17:00	4.6	1.4	1.4	-0.9	47	0.12	5.05	20.8	-9.2	108804	11295
2011	9	17	18:23	4.7	1.4	1.4	5.1	51	0.12	5.05	20.8	-8.5	108805	11295
2011	9	17	20:00	4.9	1.7	1.7	4.5	50	0.14	5.08	20.8	-7.6	108806	11295
2011	9	17	21:30	5.0	1.4	1.4	1.7	37	0.11	5.08	20.8	-6.8	108807	11295
2011	9	17	23:00	4.9	1.7	1.7	3.2	54	0.13	5.18	20.8	-6.0	108808	11295
2011	9	18	0:30	5.0	1.6	1.6	7.6	70	0.13	5.05	20.8	-5.2	108809	11295
2011	9	18	2:00	5.2	1.8	1.8	9.9	40	0.13	5.04	20.8	-4.3	108810	11295
2011	9	18	3:40	5.3	1.8	1.8	-2.5	29	0.13	5.16	20.8	-3.4	108811	11295
2011	9	18	5:12	5.5	2.0	2.0	4.4	50	0.14	5.19	20.8	-2.6	108812	11295
2011	9	18	6:55	5.3	1.9	1.9	5.0	74	0.14	5.15	20.8	-1.6	108813	11295
2011	9	20	7:20	6.8	1.8	1.8	-6.1	82	0.11	5.02	20.8	24.4	108818	11295
2011	9	20	8:23	7.2	2.3	2.2	-3.6	114	0.12	5.22	20.8	24.3	108819	11295
2011	9	20	9:23	7.0	2.0	1.9	-1.3	77	0.11	5.19	20.8	26.1	108820	11295

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	9	25	23:33	17.5	-11.1	-10.8	-5.2	-232	-0.17	7.31	12.7	-19.4	108862	11302
2011	9	26	10:00	15.2	-10.8	-10.4	16.2	-212	-0.19	7.59	12.0	-26.7	110114	11302
2011	9	26	16:00	14.7	-11.2	-10.9	-2.9	-217	-0.19	8.17	11.9	-23.3	110115	11302
2011	9	26	16:27	17.3	-11.5	-11.2	8.6	-201	-0.18	7.42	11.8	-26.6	110102	11302
2011	9	26	22:16	17.5	-11.4	-11.2	-1.5	-157	-0.17	7.46	11.8	-23.3	110103	11302
2011	9	27	10:42	17.9	-11.0	-10.9	-1.1	-160	-0.16	7.48	11.8	-16.4	108873	11302
2011	9	27	14:00	17.8	-11.4	-11.3	-0.7	-194	-0.17	7.47	11.8	-14.6	108874	11302
2011	9	27	18:18	18.2	-11.2	-11.1	6.8	-163	-0.17	7.37	11.8	-12.2	108875	11302
2011	9	27	22:36	18.3	-11.5	-11.4	1.9	-231	-0.17	7.31	11.8	-9.9	108876	11302
2011	9	28	3:11	18.3	-11.3	-11.3	-0.5	-144	-0.17	7.19	11.8	-7.3	108877	11302
2011	9	28	7:00	17.5	-11.1	-11.2	-5.3	-33	-0.18	7.16	11.8	-5.2	108878	11302
2011	9	28	11:00	17.0	-10.7	-10.7	4.2	10	-0.17	7.32	11.8	-3.0	108879	11302
2011	9	28	15:00	16.4	-11.2	-11.3	3.4	-22	-0.19	7.33	11.8	-0.8	108880	11302
2011	9	28	18:38	16.4	-12.5	-12.5	12.6	-105	-0.21	7.16	11.8	1.7	108881	11302
2011	9	28	21:37	16.2	-10.5	-10.4	8.2	-213	-0.18	7.24	11.8	2.9	108882	11302
2011	9	29	0:45	16.0	-10.3	-10.1	10.2	-309	-0.18	7.14	11.8	5.0	108883	11302
2011	9	29	4:10	16.0	-9.8	-9.6	-6.1	-326	-0.17	7.13	11.8	6.5	108884	11302
2011	9	29	7:30	15.3	-8.9	-8.7	8.7	-285	-0.16	7.11	11.8	8.6	108885	11302
2011	9	29	10:16	14.5	-8.2	-8.0	5.0	-290	-0.16	7.12	11.9	11.0	108886	11302
2011	10	6	15:24	2.6	-0.5	-0.5	-2.7	-36	-0.07	5.41	22.8	-21.9	108912	11312
2011	10	7	2:31	2.7	-0.5	-0.5	-0.2	-26	-0.06	5.50	22.8	-15.8	108915	11312
2011	10	7	22:30	2.6	-0.6	-0.6	2.5	-9	-0.10	4.69	22.8	-5.0	108917	11312
2011	10	8	6:27	2.7	-0.9	-0.9	4.2	-32	-0.14	4.70	22.8	-0.6	108918	11312
2011	10	9	18:38	2.2	-0.3	-0.3	-0.5	-2	-0.05	4.90	-15.6	-18.6	108920	11313
2011	10	9	19:15	1.7	-0.1	-0.1	2.7	18	-0.03	5.03	-15.6	-18.3	108921	11313
2011	10	10	0:50	2.1	-0.4	-0.4	3.3	37	-0.08	4.70	-15.6	-15.2	108922	11313
2011	10	10	1:30	1.8	-0.4	-0.4	-1.4	4	-0.10	4.83	-15.6	-14.9	108923	11313
2011	10	10	6:14	2.5	-0.8	-0.8	7.0	36	-0.13	4.76	-15.6	-12.3	108924	11313
2011	10	10	7:36	2.8	-1.1	-1.1	0.6	-22	-0.16	4.82	-15.6	-11.5	108925	11313
2011	10	10	14:44	3.0	-0.0	-0.0	6.8	21	-0.00	5.33	-15.6	-7.6	108926	11313
2011	10	10	16:05	3.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0	0.01	5.40	-15.6	-6.9	108927	11313
2011	10	10	20:50	3.1	0.1	0.1	6.2	11	0.01	5.74	-15.6	-4.3	108928	11313
2011	10	10	21:30	3.2	0.2	0.2	6.7	26	0.02	5.79	-15.6	-3.9	108929	11313

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	10	22	10:03	3.3	-0.9	-0.9	4.7	2	-0.11	4.61	10.9	-21.4	108981	11324
2011	10	22	17:01	2.6	-1.2	-1.2	4.2	2	-0.18	5.07	10.9	-17.6	108984	11324
2011	10	22	18:44	2.9	-0.5	-0.5	2.5	-20	-0.09	4.24	10.9	-16.6	108985	11324
2011	10	22	23:32	3.4	-1.5	-1.5	-2.5	-35	-0.19	4.68	10.9	-13.8	108986	11324
2011	10	23	4:01	3.3	-1.5	-1.5	5.1	-6	-0.21	4.40	10.9	-11.5	108987	11324
2011	10	23	12:01	3.0	-1.0	-1.0	-0.9	-23	-0.16	4.13	10.9	-7.0	108990	11324
2011	10	23	22:31	2.9	-0.8	-0.8	3.9	0	-0.14	4.00	10.9	-0.2	108995	11324
2011	10	24	3:00	2.9	-0.8	-0.8	5.9	58	-0.12	4.09	10.9	1.3	110118	11324
2011	10	24	6:29	2.4	-0.7	-0.7	2.4	11	-0.14	4.05	10.9	3.2	108997	11324
2011	10	26	14:05	5.5	-0.6	-0.6	0.9	-6	-0.03	7.91	5.7	-17.4	109024	11330
2011	10	26	16:05	5.5	-0.6	-0.6	2.9	0	-0.03	7.85	5.7	-16.3	109025	11330
2011	10	27	6:43	6.0	-0.6	-0.6	2.2	-5	-0.02	8.05	5.7	-8.2	109026	11330
2011	10	27	14:05	6.1	-0.8	-0.8	4.3	-10	-0.03	7.91	6.1	-5.2	109028	11330
2011	10	27	15:30	6.2	-0.5	-0.5	5.5	13	-0.02	7.98	6.1	-4.3	109029	11330
2011	10	27	17:00	6.2	-0.7	-0.7	6.6	20	-0.03	7.98	6.1	-3.5	109030	11330
2011	10	28	2:25	6.5	-1.4	-1.4	6.3	9	-0.05	7.86	6.1	1.7	109031	11330
2011	10	28	5:30	6.6	-1.4	-1.4	9.8	36	-0.05	7.90	6.1	3.4	109032	11330
2011	10	28	8:40	6.6	-1.5	-1.5	7.4	14	-0.06	7.89	6.1	5.2	109033	11330
2011	10	28	16:00	7.0	-0.6	-0.7	7.3	86	-0.02	7.67	6.1	9.3	109036	11330
2011	10	28	17:30	7.1	-0.8	-0.8	5.9	76	-0.03	7.64	6.1	10.1	109037	11330
2011	10	28	19:00	7.0	-0.8	-0.9	13.3	96	-0.03	7.69	6.1	10.9	109038	11330
2011	10	28	22:10	6.7	-0.9	-1.0	4.1	50	-0.04	7.74	6.1	12.7	109039	11330
2011	10	29	0:00	6.7	-0.9	-0.9	8.6	54	-0.03	7.69	6.1	13.7	109040	11330
2011	10	29	10:00	6.4	-1.0	-1.0	2.7	-5	-0.04	7.82	6.1	19.3	109043	11330
2011	10	29	12:30	6.3	-0.6	-0.6	7.2	29	-0.02	7.83	5.5	21.1	109045	11330
2011	10	29	14:01	6.3	-0.4	-0.4	5.2	32	-0.02	7.88	5.5	21.9	109046	11330
2011	10	29	15:30	6.5	-0.4	-0.4	5.8	27	-0.01	7.81	5.5	22.7	109047	11330
2011	10	29	23:30	6.7	-0.8	-0.8	3.4	32	-0.03	7.58	5.5	27.2	109050	11330
2011	11	6	8:02	13.8	-0.1	-0.1	5.8	24	-0.00	7.74	19.0	-27.9	109116	11339
2011	11	6	9:55	9.2	2.2	2.1	7.6	68	0.07	7.09	19.0	-26.9	109117	11339
2011	11	6	12:00	13.1	-0.5	-0.5	3.6	4	-0.01	7.87	19.0	-25.7	109118	11339
2011	11	6	20:00	12.8	0.7	0.7	1.8	34	0.01	7.81	19.0	-21.3	109120	11339
2011	11	7	0:00	12.9	1.6	1.5	6.1	98	0.03	7.80	19.0	-19.1	109121	11339

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	11	7	3:40	12.5	2.2	2.2	12.4	154	0.05	7.66	19.0	-17.1	109122	11339
2011	11	7	8:10	12.3	2.4	2.4	10.5	126	0.05	7.67	19.0	-14.6	109123	11339
2011	11	7	12:10	11.6	1.5	1.5	8.8	104	0.03	7.67	19.0	-12.4	109124	11339
2011	11	7	15:30	8.3	3.4	3.3	15.0	197	0.11	7.20	19.0	-10.8	109125	11339
2011	11	8	7:30	11.2	1.0	1.0	8.8	29	0.02	7.77	18.9	-1.9	109129	11339
2011	11	9	23:10	10.3	2.5	2.5	3.7	94	0.07	7.27	18.7	18.9	109142	11339
2011	11	10	10:02	10.4	-0.7	-0.6	-3.8	-114	-0.02	7.32	18.7	27.4	109145	11339
2011	11	23	0:15	1.3	0.1	0.1	-0.2	6	0.04	4.67	-25.4	12.6	109214	11352
2011	11	24	10:20	3.5	-3.1	-3.1	2.9	-124	-0.35	5.00	16.5	-27.5	109216	11356
2011	11	25	0:05	3.9	-3.6	-3.5	-0.6	-151	-0.37	5.07	16.4	-22.8	109217	11356
2011	11	26	0:21	3.6	-3.4	-3.3	-4.8	-145	-0.36	5.20	16.4	-9.4	109219	11356
2011	11	27	20:03	2.0	-1.1	-1.1	2.8	-44	-0.23	4.72	16.8	15.2	109221	11356
2011	11	28	0:05	1.4	-0.7	-0.7	1.0	-29	-0.21	4.46	16.8	17.5	109222	11356
2011	11	28	6:50	1.8	-0.9	-0.8	3.4	-22	-0.20	4.67	16.8	21.1	109223	11356
2011	11	28	18:42	1.6	-0.6	-0.6	1.3	-1	-0.17	4.39	16.8	27.6	109224	11356
2011	11	29	9:45	1.7	-0.2	-0.2	3.3	36	-0.04	4.55	18.3	-16.0	109226	11361
2011	11	29	23:15	1.8	0.0	-0.0	10.2	64	0.00	4.26	18.3	-8.6	109227	11361
2011	12	1	13:32	3.0	-0.4	-0.3	6.1	8	-0.05	5.19	18.6	11.3	109249	11361
2011	12	1	15:10	3.0	-0.3	-0.3	6.9	29	-0.04	5.14	18.6	12.2	109250	11361
2011	12	1	18:30	3.2	-0.6	-0.6	4.9	27	-0.07	5.21	18.6	14.1	109251	11361
2011	12	1	22:00	3.0	-0.9	-0.9	4.4	-5	-0.11	5.40	18.6	16.0	109252	11361
2011	12	2	1:00	3.0	-0.9	-0.9	3.6	0	-0.10	5.56	18.6	17.6	109253	11361
2011	12	2	4:00	2.8	-0.7	-0.7	6.1	6	-0.09	5.78	18.6	19.3	109254	11361
2011	12	2	7:20	2.7	-0.7	-0.7	2.2	5	-0.09	5.74	18.6	21.1	109255	11361
2011	12	2	11:00	2.6	-0.5	-0.5	4.7	12	-0.07	5.53	18.6	23.1	109256	11361
2011	12	2	14:00	2.6	-0.3	-0.3	5.1	21	-0.05	5.44	18.6	24.8	109257	11361
2011	12	2	19:20	2.2	-0.1	-0.1	6.5	41	-0.02	4.99	18.6	27.7	109258	11361
2011	12	6	9:56	7.3	6.4	6.4	13.8	207	0.25	7.11	-21.8	11.3	109263	11363
2011	12	6	16:53	7.2	6.6	6.5	24.1	309	0.25	7.37	-21.8	14.8	109264	11363
2011	12	7	6:59	5.9	6.0	6.0	16.2	224	0.27	7.59	-21.8	22.4	109266	11363
2011	12	12	17:31	3.5	1.6	1.6	4.7	74	0.16	5.71	-18.3	-22.8	109269	11374
2011	12	12	19:01	3.6	1.7	1.7	4.1	64	0.16	5.85	-18.3	-20.6	109270	11374
2011	12	12	20:40	3.6	1.6	1.6	1.2	53	0.15	5.89	-18.3	-19.7	109271	11374

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2011	12	12	23:50	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.2	42	0.15	5.82	-18.3	-12.3	109272	11374
2011	12	13	2:50	3.6	1.5	1.5	2.5	48	0.15	5.80	-18.3	-16.4	109273	11374
2011	12	13	6:15	3.6	1.5	1.5	5.7	38	0.14	5.69	-18.3	-14.5	109274	11374
2011	12	14	0:20	3.1	1.2	1.2	2.5	40	0.13	5.76	-18.3	-4.7	109275	11374
2011	12	14	5:00	2.9	1.3	1.3	2.4	60	0.16	5.66	-18.3	-2.1	109276	11374
2011	12	14	8:10	2.9	1.2	1.2	0.4	33	0.15	5.57	-18.3	-0.4	109277	11374
2011	12	14	18:33	2.6	1.2	1.2	2.6	42	0.17	5.31	-18.3	5.3	109278	11374
2011	12	16	3:00	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.8	31	0.19	4.92	-18.3	24.6	109279	11374
2011	12	16	6:22	1.9	0.9	0.9	2.8	26	0.18	4.90	-18.3	26.4	109280	11374
2011	12	20	10:15	3.0	-0.3	-0.3	6.7	14	-0.05	4.66	-18.1	-9.2	109291	11382
2011	12	20	20:25	3.3	0.7	0.6	9.3	90	0.09	4.64	-18.1	-3.6	109292	11382
2011	12	21	2:35	4.7	1.1	1.0	2.6	112	0.09	4.93	-18.1	-0.2	109293	11382
2011	12	21	4:35	4.8	1.3	1.2	7.5	152	0.11	4.97	-18.1	0.8	109294	11382
2011	12	21	11:25	4.2	1.8	1.7	10.4	125	0.17	4.93	-18.1	4.5	109295	11382
2011	12	22	4:46	4.5	1.4	1.3	6.0	142	0.11	5.42	-18.1	14.0	109296	11382
2011	12	22	8:15	4.0	0.5	0.5	5.5	65	0.04	5.29	-18.1	15.9	109297	11382
2011	12	22	10:29	4.3	0.5	0.5	1.0	31	0.04	5.19	-18.1	17.1	109298	11382
2011	12	23	2:09	3.4	-0.3	-0.3	1.9	18	-0.03	5.52	-18.1	25.7	109299	11382
2011	12	24	4:21	7.1	3.4	3.4	1.1	40	0.12	8.12	13.2	-23.2	109303	11384
2012	1	1	21:30	3.5	3.3	3.3	2.2	79	0.31	5.96	-25.0	-29.8	109353	11389
2012	1	2	3:25	3.4	3.1	3.1	1.6	63	0.33	5.62	-25.0	-26.7	109354	11389
2012	1	2	10:00	3.0	2.6	2.6	7.7	60	0.32	5.33	-25.0	-23.1	109355	11389
2012	1	2	18:30	3.0	2.3	2.3	0.3	35	0.31	5.05	-25.0	-18.6	109356	11389
2012	1	3	2:30	2.6	1.6	1.6	0.5	3	0.24	5.03	-25.0	-14.3	109357	11389
2012	1	10	18:35	4.8	-1.7	-1.6	-2.3	-97	-0.12	5.96	11.2	24.6	109378	11391
2012	1	13	17:10	1.3	-0.0	-0.0	2.1	4	-0.01	4.18	19.2	-1.6	109385	11395
2012	1	19	7:30	4.0	-3.6	-3.5	-2.6	-119	-0.33	5.33	17.9	-25.6	109406	11407
2012	1	19	19:06	4.4	-1.3	-1.2	1.0	-43	-0.09	6.58	17.6	-16.4	109409	11407
2012	1	20	6:34	3.6	-3.7	-3.7	-4.3	-110	-0.39	5.38	17.6	-10.1	109412	11407
2012	1	20	18:20	4.7	-1.7	-1.7	2.8	-60	-0.10	6.97	17.6	-3.7	109413	11407
2012	1	22	16:48	2.8	-1.1	-1.1	4.1	-21	-0.13	5.71	17.6	21.8	109421	11407
2012	1	30	18:05	2.9	-0.3	-0.3	2.4	-5	-0.03	6.72	18.6	-26.8	109448	11410
2012	1	30	23:11	3.1	-0.7	-0.7	2.7	-11	-0.06	6.79	18.6	-24.0	109450	11410

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	1	31	3:15	3.1	-0.5	-0.5	1.5	-2	-0.04	6.94	18.6	-21.8	109451	11410
2012	1	31	4:56	3.4	-0.8	-0.8	3.1	6	-0.07	6.77	18.6	-20.6	109452	11410
2012	1	31	8:11	3.2	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	0	-0.04	7.00	18.6	-19.0	109453	11410
2012	1	31	23:11	3.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-11	-0.02	6.79	18.6	-10.8	109456	11410
2012	2	1	0:36	3.8	-0.7	-0.7	1.5	-11	-0.05	6.70	18.6	-9.8	109457	11410
2012	2	1	2:16	3.7	-0.6	-0.6	3.4	-7	-0.04	6.84	18.6	-9.1	109458	11410
2012	2	1	7:06	3.8	-0.8	-0.8	2.3	-7	-0.06	6.61	18.6	-6.3	109459	11410
2012	2	1	8:51	3.6	-0.3	-0.3	1.3	4	-0.02	6.95	18.6	-5.5	109460	11410
2012	2	1	19:15	3.7	-0.4	-0.4	4.0	-8	-0.03	6.94	18.6	0.2	109461	11410
2012	2	1	23:40	3.7	-0.3	-0.3	1.6	-2	-0.03	6.90	18.6	2.6	109462	11410
2012	2	2	2:50	3.5	-0.4	-0.4	2.3	6	-0.03	6.84	18.6	4.3	109463	11410
2012	2	2	7:45	3.6	-0.4	-0.4	1.5	-7	-0.03	6.76	18.6	7.0	109464	11410
2012	2	18	11:08	1.4	-0.5	-0.5	-0.1	-25	-0.14	4.82	10.0	-4.6	110129	11420
2012	2	19	6:33	1.3	-0.4	-0.3	0.4	-13	-0.12	4.72	10.1	3.0	110130	11420
2012	2	19	18:30	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.7	-20	-0.12	4.33	10.1	9.7	110131	11420
2012	2	20	20:43	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.6	-9	-0.08	4.20	10.1	24.2	110134	11420
2012	3	1	19:00	1.8	-0.8	-0.8	3.2	-101	-0.25	3.83	11.8	-2.6	110181	11427
2012	3	2	11:00	1.7	-0.6	-0.5	2.4	-110	-0.20	3.41	11.8	6.3	110182	11427
2012	3	2	18:12	1.4	-0.3	-0.3	2.5	-49	-0.12	3.92	11.8	10.2	110183	11427
2012	3	7	2:21	17.7	-37.7	-37.4	-12.7	-1020	-0.57	7.37	16.8	-28.6	110195	11429
2012	3	7	8:00	18.0	-35.9	-35.5	-16.8	-1078	-0.55	7.15	16.8	-25.5	110218	11429
2012	3	7	9:00	18.2	-35.8	-35.5	-11.8	-1036	-0.55	7.08	16.8	-24.9	110199	11429
2012	3	7	14:29	17.1	-33.0	-32.7	-3.7	-950	-0.56	6.80	16.8	-21.9	110231	11429
2012	3	7	16:00	17.9	-33.0	-32.6	-2.6	-1044	-0.54	6.75	16.8	-21.1	110202	11429
2012	3	8	8:00	15.1	-23.9	-23.6	1.7	-717	-0.49	6.39	16.8	-12.3	110207	11429
2012	3	16	12:18	2.4	-1.0	-1.0	-0.7	-27	-0.15	5.46	10.4	-4.6	110220	11433
2012	3	16	14:39	2.4	-0.9	-0.9	-2.3	-42	-0.14	5.39	10.4	-3.3	110221	11433
2012	3	16	21:18	2.2	-0.8	-0.8	-3.2	-33	-0.14	5.23	10.4	0.4	110222	11433
2012	3	17	3:29	2.0	-0.6	-0.6	-1.0	-20	-0.12	5.10	10.4	3.8	110223	11433
2012	3	18	15:00	1.5	-0.5	-0.5	-1.1	-12	-0.14	4.45	10.4	23.5	110228	11433
2012	3	27	23:15	3.1	0.5	0.5	0.3	31	0.05	5.93	-23.3	-26.5	110259	11445
2012	3	28	10:17	3.0	0.7	0.7	-0.3	28	0.07	6.34	-23.3	-20.6	110260	11445
2012	3	28	12:00	2.9	0.8	0.8	1.4	46	0.09	6.42	-23.3	-19.7	110261	11445

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	3	28	14:00	2.9	0.9	0.9	0.6	40	0.09	6.62	-23.3	-18.5	110262	11445
2012	3	28	22:17	3.1	0.9	0.8	4.6	43	0.08	6.68	-23.3	-14.1	110263	11445
2012	4	13	19:20	2.8	-0.5	-0.5	1.8	-18	-0.08	4.66	7.7	13.4	110320	11455
2012	4	14	9:30	2.6	-0.2	-0.2	-1.4	14	-0.04	4.60	5.6	24.0	110321	11455
2012	4	14	12:00	2.6	-0.3	-0.3	-0.2	-11	-0.05	4.67	5.6	25.4	110322	11455
2012	4	14	15:00	2.6	-0.3	-0.3	1.8	-15	-0.05	4.63	5.6	27.0	110323	11455
2012	4	14	16:50	2.6	-0.4	-0.4	5.2	6	-0.07	4.63	5.6	28.1	110324	11455
2012	4	20	18:45	6.1	-0.5	-0.5	9.5	79	-0.02	7.14	-15.3	-7.3	110354	11459
2012	4	20	22:00	6.1	-0.7	-0.7	8.0	63	-0.03	7.22	-15.3	-5.5	110355	11459
2012	4	22	1:03	7.6	-2.1	-2.1	6.9	3	-0.07	7.40	-15.3	9.3	110361	11459
2012	4	22	4:43	7.7	-1.8	-1.8	8.5	-32	-0.06	7.42	-15.3	11.3	110362	11459
2012	4	22	8:00	7.5	-1.9	-1.9	4.3	-42	-0.07	7.55	-15.3	13.1	110363	11459
2012	4	22	12:00	7.4	-2.2	-2.2	-1.1	-24	-0.08	7.64	-15.3	15.3	110364	11459
2012	4	22	16:40	7.2	-2.3	-2.3	8.9	-13	-0.08	7.52	-15.3	17.9	110365	11459
2012	4	22	20:00	6.9	-2.4	-2.4	6.9	3	-0.09	7.53	-15.3	19.7	110366	11459
2012	4	22	23:30	6.7	-2.0	-2.1	5.4	24	-0.08	7.43	-15.3	21.6	110367	11459
2012	4	23	4:00	6.6	-1.8	-1.9	5.9	34	-0.08	7.35	-15.3	24.1	110368	11459
2012	4	23	7:20	6.7	-2.3	-2.3	1.3	-9	-0.09	7.31	-15.3	25.9	110369	11459
2012	4	23	12:00	6.5	-2.3	-2.3	-3.3	-32	-0.09	7.55	-15.3	28.4	110370	11459
2012	4	26	7:20	3.4	-2.6	-2.5	-1.6	-122	-0.31	4.86	-17.6	28.2	110381	11465
2012	5	2	10:00	6.1	5.0	4.9	5.0	185	0.23	7.17	-22.9	-29.7	110413	11471
2012	5	9	22:20	10.2	-5.9	-5.5	-1.0	-511	-0.21	5.58	10.6	-22.7	110473	11476
2012	5	10	8:00	9.3	-7.2	-6.8	-2.5	-546	-0.30	5.17	10.6	-18.2	110474	11476
2012	5	10	9:39	9.1	-7.1	-6.7	-0.8	-520	-0.30	5.24	10.6	-17.3	110475	11476
2012	5	10	11:14	9.0	-7.1	-6.6	-0.8	-466	-0.29	5.34	10.6	-16.5	110476	11476
2012	5	10	13:00	3.9	-3.0	-2.9	-2.4	-237	-0.34	4.53	10.6	-16.4	110477	11476
2012	5	11	0:51	7.4	-6.6	-6.2	-9.6	-536	-0.32	5.51	10.6	-8.9	110479	11476
2012	5	11	2:01	7.4	-6.5	-6.2	-9.9	-499	-0.31	5.56	10.6	-8.3	110480	11476
2012	5	11	3:40	7.6	-6.0	-5.7	-1.7	-446	-0.29	5.50	10.6	-7.3	110481	11476
2012	5	11	10:15	7.4	-5.7	-5.4	-12.7	-439	-0.28	5.41	10.6	-3.7	110483	11476
2012	5	11	13:30	7.4	-5.9	-5.6	-1.4	-405	-0.29	5.38	10.6	-1.8	110484	11476
2012	5	11	15:21	7.2	-5.8	-5.6	-3.0	-404	-0.30	5.46	10.6	-0.9	110486	11476
2012	5	11	23:30	16.9	-28.4	-28.1	-20.1	-702	-0.44	7.60	8.1	6.0	110488	11476

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	5	12	2:38	16.7	-27.3	-27.1	-13.1	-615	-0.43	7.55	8.1	7.7	110489	11476
2012	5	12	9:13	15.9	-23.3	-23.1	-8.8	-620	-0.38	7.63	8.1	11.4	110490	11476
2012	5	12	12:30	15.3	-21.6	-21.4	-14.0	-630	-0.38	7.41	8.6	13.6	110491	11476
2012	5	12	19:20	13.1	-11.9	-11.9	-21.1	-378	-0.24	7.56	8.6	17.3	110493	11476
2012	5	12	22:30	12.3	-9.8	-9.8	-5.2	-275	-0.21	7.57	8.6	19.1	110494	11476
2012	5	13	1:45	11.6	-9.0	-9.0	-7.3	-279	-0.21	7.50	8.6	20.9	110495	11476
2012	5	13	5:00	11.2	-6.7	-6.7	-12.3	-253	-0.16	7.34	8.6	22.7	110496	11476
2012	5	13	8:15	11.0	-6.9	-6.8	-6.1	-243	-0.17	7.33	8.6	24.5	110497	11476
2012	5	13	11:30	10.4	-8.8	-8.7	-13.7	-314	-0.24	6.98	8.4	17.3	110498	11476
2012	5	13	14:46	9.7	-5.8	-5.7	-2.4	-201	-0.17	7.17	8.6	28.1	110499	11476
2012	5	17	19:11	4.7	-1.4	-1.4	5.4	8	-0.09	6.51	12.2	-1.4	110515	11482
2012	5	17	22:20	5.1	-1.8	-1.8	5.2	-15	-0.10	6.70	12.2	0.4	110516	11482
2012	5	18	1:30	5.5	-2.1	-2.1	3.5	-21	-0.11	6.71	12.2	2.1	110517	11482
2012	5	18	4:47	5.7	-2.0	-2.0	3.5	-24	-0.10	6.82	12.2	3.9	110518	11482
2012	5	18	18:21	5.8	-0.8	-0.8	6.3	23	-0.04	7.33	12.2	11.4	110520	11482
2012	5	18	21:30	5.9	-1.1	-1.1	7.8	-1	-0.05	7.45	12.2	13.2	110521	11482
2012	5	19	0:40	5.9	-1.1	-1.1	9.7	16	-0.05	7.54	12.2	14.9	110522	11482
2012	5	19	3:50	6.0	-1.0	-1.0	4.4	4	-0.04	7.57	12.2	16.7	110523	11482
2012	5	25	7:33	2.7	-0.3	-0.3	0.9	-13	-0.04	5.44	15.0	15.3	110549	11486
2012	5	25	19:11	2.7	-0.2	-0.1	0.4	-10	-0.02	5.29	15.0	21.7	110553	11486
2012	5	29	12:11	1.9	0.3	0.3	4.8	59	0.08	4.82	-15.7	-24.8	110559	11492
2012	5	29	15:32	2.4	0.2	0.2	2.3	17	0.03	5.67	-15.6	-23.6	110560	11492
2012	5	29	18:50	2.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	15	0.06	5.58	-15.6	-21.9	110561	11492
2012	5	29	21:57	2.4	0.2	0.2	4.2	36	0.03	5.61	-15.6	-19.4	110562	11492
2012	5	30	1:20	2.2	0.2	0.1	4.0	36	0.03	5.69	-15.6	-17.8	110563	11492
2012	5	30	4:22	2.3	0.1	0.1	3.6	31	0.02	5.57	-15.6	-15.9	110564	11492
2012	5	30	6:12	2.4	-0.0	-0.1	4.3	29	-0.00	5.32	-15.6	-14.9	110565	11492
2012	5	30	9:20	2.4	-0.0	-0.0	0.3	19	-0.00	5.22	-15.6	-13.2	110566	11492
2012	5	30	19:22	2.3	-0.2	-0.2	4.5	29	-0.03	5.15	-15.6	-7.7	110568	11492
2012	5	30	20:57	2.3	-0.2	-0.2	6.6	34	-0.03	5.13	-15.6	-6.8	110569	11492
2012	5	30	22:40	2.1	-0.2	-0.2	2.5	17	-0.04	5.17	-15.6	-6.1	110570	11492
2012	5	31	1:52	2.2	-0.1	-0.1	2.9	35	-0.02	5.05	-15.6	-4.1	110572	11492
2012	5	31	3:20	2.2	-0.1	-0.1	4.8	46	-0.02	5.04	-15.6	-3.3	110573	11492

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	5	31	5:00	2.2	-0.1	-0.2	3.3	35	-0.02	5.08	-15.6	-2.4	110574	11492
2012	5	31	13:10	2.0	-0.2	-0.2	6.3	39	-0.03	5.27	-15.6	2.0	110576	11492
2012	6	3	23:15	2.1	-0.2	-0.2	3.5	-6	-0.04	4.34	11.3	-28.7	110605	11496
2012	6	4	4:03	2.4	-0.1	-0.1	2.5	6	-0.03	4.29	11.3	-25.1	110606	11496
2012	6	4	10:40	2.6	0.1	0.1	7.9	47	0.02	4.66	11.3	-21.5	110607	11496
2012	6	4	15:38	2.5	0.1	0.1	2.5	24	0.03	4.74	11.3	-19.2	110608	11496
2012	6	4	22:13	2.4	0.3	0.2	1.8	27	0.05	4.56	11.3	-15.7	110609	11496
2012	6	5	3:03	2.4	0.4	0.4	6.7	37	0.07	4.37	11.3	-12.4	110610	11496
2012	6	5	8:00	2.4	0.5	0.5	4.0	23	0.10	4.37	11.3	-9.7	110611	11496
2012	6	6	7:03	1.3	0.1	0.1	2.5	6	0.02	3.66	13.0	-6.8	110615	11496
2012	6	7	14:15	3.2	-1.5	-1.5	1.4	-33	-0.16	5.87	-19.7	11.8	110616	11494
2012	6	8	6:29	2.8	-1.1	-1.1	0.4	-8	-0.13	6.06	-19.7	21.4	110617	11494
2012	6	8	11:22	2.7	-0.7	-0.7	-0.6	-3	-0.08	6.05	-19.7	24.1	110618	11494
2012	6	9	17:05	2.7	0.3	0.2	-1.6	85	0.07	3.34	13.7	29.1	110620	11499
2012	7	3	10:35	5.6	-2.3	-2.3	4.6	-44	-0.14	5.90	13.5	14.9	110728	11513
2012	7	3	13:48	5.5	-2.1	-2.1	-2.2	-46	-0.13	5.96	13.5	16.7	110729	11513
2012	7	3	17:17	5.3	-1.9	-1.9	2.4	-27	-0.12	6.02	13.5	18.5	110730	11513
2012	7	3	23:41	5.2	-2.4	-2.4	3.2	-45	-0.15	5.99	13.5	22.2	110733	11513
2012	7	4	2:56	5.1	-2.8	-2.8	-2.4	-86	-0.18	5.98	13.5	24.0	110734	11513
2012	7	4	6:27	4.9	-2.8	-2.8	-1.3	-61	-0.18	6.10	13.5	25.9	110735	11513
2012	7	4	9:30	4.9	-2.8	-2.8	1.4	-76	-0.19	6.01	13.5	27.6	110736	11513
2012	7	4	19:30	10.8	-3.8	-3.8	-0.1	-148	-0.11	6.37	-18.7	19.5	110740	11515
2012	7	4	22:40	11.1	-3.3	-3.4	-0.6	15	-0.10	6.20	-18.7	21.2	110741	11515
2012	7	5	1:55	10.9	-2.5	-2.6	4.0	71	-0.08	6.01	-18.7	23.0	110742	11515
2012	7	5	3:45	11.2	-2.7	-2.8	9.4	48	-0.08	5.97	-18.7	24.0	110743	11515
2012	7	5	6:51	11.5	-4.3	-4.4	-0.1	-104	-0.13	5.92	-18.7	25.7	110744	11515
2012	7	10	23:10	15.4	37.4	37.1	23.6	774	0.54	8.97	-19.5	-21.4	110804	11520
2012	7	11	17:35	14.8	33.7	33.5	30.2	760	0.51	8.95	-19.6	-14.1	110805	11520
2012	7	11	20:26	15.8	37.8	37.6	32.7	759	0.52	9.20	-19.5	-9.8	110807	11520
2012	7	12	11:12	14.9	37.0	36.7	19.6	686	0.51	9.75	-19.5	-1.9	110808	11520
2012	7	13	0:20	12.9	33.4	33.2	24.5	603	0.52	9.90	-19.5	5.2	110809	11520
2012	7	13	0:47	13.4	36.5	36.3	16.8	548	0.54	10.10	-19.5	4.6	110810	11520
2012	7	13	12:02	13.2	34.8	34.6	19.3	568	0.55	9.60	-19.5	11.6	110811	11520

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	7	14	16:00	10.5	22.2	22.1	11.7	363	0.43	9.85	-19.5	26.8	110812	11520
2012	7	21	10:46	1.9	0.7	0.7	5.4	61	0.15	5.26	-21.5	-7.1	110834	11525
2012	7	21	11:53	1.2	0.6	0.6	5.2	57	0.24	4.19	-21.5	-5.0	110835	11525
2012	7	21	13:30	1.4	0.6	0.6	5.0	55	0.18	4.25	-21.5	-4.2	110836	11525
2012	7	21	15:30	1.4	0.5	0.5	4.9	46	0.17	4.44	-21.5	-3.1	110837	11525
2012	7	21	17:00	2.0	0.7	0.7	5.8	58	0.13	5.56	-21.5	-3.3	110838	11525
2012	7	21	21:57	1.3	0.5	0.5	6.2	53	0.17	4.25	-21.5	0.4	110839	11525
2012	7	21	23:30	1.7	0.5	0.5	8.9	78	0.12	4.52	-21.5	1.2	110840	11525
2012	7	22	1:00	1.6	0.5	0.4	7.2	76	0.13	4.48	-21.5	2.1	110841	11525
2012	7	22	2:38	1.6	0.5	0.5	4.2	66	0.14	4.44	-21.5	2.9	110842	11525
2012	7	22	4:16	1.6	0.5	0.5	7.2	68	0.13	4.49	-21.5	3.8	110843	11525
2012	7	22	6:15	1.9	0.4	0.4	6.5	61	0.08	5.26	-21.5	4.9	110844	11525
2012	7	22	7:33	2.0	0.4	0.4	2.4	36	0.07	5.21	-21.5	5.6	110845	11525
2012	7	22	9:12	1.9	0.4	0.4	5.8	37	0.08	5.07	-21.5	6.5	110846	11525
2012	7	22	19:16	1.7	0.2	0.2	2.7	34	0.06	4.67	-21.5	11.9	110852	11525
2012	7	22	22:30	1.7	0.1	0.1	2.4	23	0.04	4.78	-21.5	13.7	110853	11525
2012	7	22	23:58	1.6	0.1	0.1	2.4	23	0.02	4.72	-21.5	14.5	110854	11525
2012	7	23	6:32	1.4	0.1	0.0	0.5	10	0.02	4.67	-21.5	18.0	110855	11525
2012	7	23	8:11	1.4	0.0	0.0	1.3	9	0.00	4.55	-21.5	18.9	110856	11525
2012	7	23	15:07	1.2	-0.0	-0.0	1.1	7	-0.01	4.36	-21.5	22.7	110862	11525
2012	7	23	16:40	1.1	-0.0	-0.0	3.5	11	-0.01	4.39	-21.5	23.5	110863	11525
2012	7	23	18:28	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	7	0.00	4.36	-21.5	24.1	110864	11525
2012	7	23	21:32	0.9	0.1	0.1	-0.3	5	0.03	4.32	-21.5	26.1	110865	11525
2012	7	24	0:35	0.8	0.0	0.0	1.3	12	0.02	4.40	-21.5	27.8	110866	11525
2012	7	24	6:05	0.8	0.1	0.1	3.2	29	0.08	4.53	-21.4	29.0	110867	11525
2012	7	25	11:03	1.5	0.4	0.4	10.5	71	0.14	3.71	-21.3	-8.7	110880	11526
2012	7	25	12:41	1.6	0.4	0.4	10.7	74	0.13	3.63	-21.3	-7.8	110881	11526
2012	7	25	14:30	1.6	0.3	0.3	12.2	58	0.11	3.74	-21.3	-6.8	110882	11526
2012	7	25	16:20	1.6	0.3	0.3	10.0	50	0.12	3.77	-21.3	-5.8	110883	11526
2012	7	25	19:32	1.6	0.3	0.3	10.7	66	0.10	3.76	-21.3	-4.0	110885	11526
2012	7	25	21:10	1.6	0.3	0.2	10.5	62	0.08	3.80	-21.3	-3.2	110886	11526
2012	7	26	6:45	1.5	0.3	0.3	8.6	63	0.11	3.68	-21.3	2.0	110887	11526
2012	7	28	6:22	3.8	-0.5	-0.5	5.3	11	-0.05	5.52	-21.6	-27.6	110915	11532

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	7	28	7:59	3.8	-0.2	-0.2	7.6	39	-0.02	5.44	-21.6	-26.7	110916	11532
2012	7	30	9:14	6.7	-5.6	-5.5	-5.5	-123	-0.22	7.61	-22.1	-30.3	110926	11532
2012	7	30	12:31	6.5	-4.4	-4.4	0.9	-79	-0.18	7.51	-22.1	-28.5	110927	11532
2012	7	30	16:05	6.7	-5.4	-5.4	4.1	-32	-0.22	7.24	-22.1	-26.9	110928	11532
2012	8	11	12:26	2.2	1.1	1.0	7.8	113	0.28	3.46	-13.5	-15.2	111018	11542
2012	8	11	18:38	2.1	1.0	0.9	7.9	124	0.28	3.41	-13.5	-11.8	111019	11542
2012	8	11	23:25	1.9	0.9	0.8	13.2	135	0.26	3.39	-13.4	-4.7	111020	11542
2012	8	12	6:21	1.9	0.7	0.7	7.2	83	0.22	3.32	-13.5	-5.4	111022	11542
2012	8	12	12:11	1.8	0.5	0.5	6.8	78	0.17	3.38	-13.5	-2.2	111024	11542
2012	8	12	18:49	1.7	0.4	0.4	6.4	61	0.16	3.19	-13.5	1.5	111025	11542
2012	8	14	1:05	1.1	0.2	0.2	3.2	24	0.10	3.22	-13.6	18.1	111035	11542
2012	8	14	6:15	0.9	0.2	0.1	2.0	17	0.10	3.18	-13.5	21.0	111036	11542
2012	8	14	14:35	5.2	5.7	5.8	7.5	114	0.30	7.32	21.3	15.0	111038	11543
2012	8	14	18:09	5.2	5.5	5.5	8.9	109	0.29	7.27	21.3	16.9	111039	11543
2012	8	22	23:38	0.9	0.1	0.1	1.4	14	0.09	3.69	15.5	6.4	111062	11546
2012	8	28	2:30	1.4	0.3	0.3	0.4	17	0.10	4.39	15.7	27.5	111106	11554
2012	8	28	4:40	1.4	0.3	0.3	3.6	22	0.10	4.35	15.6	28.7	111107	11554
2012	9	1	10:00	2.0	-0.9	-0.9	1.3	-17	-0.28	3.37	1.1	-4.2	111115	11560
2012	9	1	11:30	1.9	-0.6	-0.6	1.7	-13	-0.21	3.17	1.1	-3.4	111116	11560
2012	9	1	13:00	1.9	-0.7	-0.7	-4.8	-44	-0.23	3.08	1.1	-2.5	111117	11560
2012	9	2	9:05	2.8	-1.8	-1.7	6.3	-77	-0.37	3.50	1.1	8.6	111118	11560
2012	9	2	11:00	2.9	-2.1	-2.0	4.8	-164	-0.41	3.50	1.1	9.7	111119	11560
2012	9	2	13:00	2.9	-2.2	-2.1	-1.2	-176	-0.43	3.53	1.1	10.8	111120	11560
2012	9	4	3:40	5.5	1.8	1.8	10.7	11	0.11	6.17	-17.5	-28.7	111125	11564
2012	9	4	7:00	5.0	1.7	1.7	7.1	7	0.11	6.26	-17.5	-26.9	111126	11564
2012	9	4	15:40	4.7	1.8	1.9	7.1	27	0.12	6.24	-17.5	-22.1	111129	11564
2012	9	5	7:30	3.6	1.1	1.1	13.8	48	0.10	6.20	-17.5	-13.5	111130	11564
2012	9	6	8:14	2.9	1.0	1.0	6.9	21	0.12	5.78	-17.5	-0.0	111133	11564
2012	9	7	7:06	2.6	0.4	0.4	3.6	17	0.06	4.52	-15.1	16.5	111136	11564
2012	9	22	23:13	4.3	-0.3	-0.3	0.1	-12	-0.02	6.48	6.8	-13.3	111182	11575
2012	9	23	4:05	4.2	-0.3	-0.3	2.9	-15	-0.02	6.62	6.3	-21.7	111183	11575
2012	9	23	8:40	4.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.7	-21	-0.02	6.63	6.3	-19.1	111184	11575
2012	9	23	13:30	4.1	-0.2	-0.2	3.3	3	-0.01	6.60	6.3	-16.4	111185	11575

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	9	23	14:35	3.6	0.0	0.0	3.6	9	0.00	6.94	4.9	-13.1	111186	11575
2012	9	23	19:05	4.0	-0.4	-0.4	6.1	-9	-0.03	6.67	6.3	-13.3	111187	11575
2012	9	24	0:05	4.2	-0.3	-0.3	5.2	-4	-0.02	6.58	6.3	-10.6	111188	11575
2012	9	24	4:30	4.4	-0.4	-0.4	4.7	-8	-0.02	6.59	6.3	-8.1	111189	11575
2012	9	24	10:14	4.7	-0.1	-0.1	6.8	28	-0.01	6.59	6.3	-4.9	111190	11575
2012	9	24	13:20	4.7	-0.2	-0.2	7.2	22	-0.01	6.50	6.3	-3.2	111191	11575
2012	9	24	14:35	4.3	0.1	0.1	3.9	22	0.00	6.68	4.9	0.3	111192	11575
2012	9	24	23:35	4.6	-0.7	-0.7	5.1	-10	-0.05	6.50	6.3	2.5	111193	11575
2012	9	25	5:11	4.7	-0.8	-0.8	3.6	-25	-0.05	6.41	6.3	5.6	111195	11575
2012	9	25	12:49	4.2	-0.9	-0.9	4.1	-42	-0.06	6.65	7.6	10.1	111196	11575
2012	9	25	20:22	3.9	-0.9	-0.9	3.2	-33	-0.07	6.68	7.6	14.2	111198	11575
2012	9	26	7:25	3.7	-1.2	-1.2	-0.9	-51	-0.10	6.53	7.6	20.4	111201	11575
2012	9	26	12:30	3.6	-1.2	-1.2	0.2	-53	-0.10	6.41	7.6	23.2	111202	11575
2012	9	30	5:30	6.4	3.4	3.4	1.2	111	0.13	7.73	-12.2	-15.1	111223	11582
2012	9	30	8:50	6.5	3.4	3.4	-0.0	98	0.13	7.79	-12.9	-27.8	111224	11582
2012	9	30	10:59	6.4	3.3	3.3	-0.4	101	0.13	7.84	-12.9	-26.6	111225	11582
2012	9	30	13:30	6.4	3.6	3.6	3.9	109	0.14	7.82	-12.9	-25.1	111226	11582
2012	9	30	14:34	3.6	1.1	1.1	3.7	53	0.09	6.66	-10.6	0.3	111227	11579
2012	9	30	17:56	6.2	3.5	3.5	2.8	113	0.15	7.79	-12.9	-22.8	111228	11582
2012	9	30	20:40	6.5	3.5	3.4	4.4	106	0.13	7.96	-12.9	-21.3	111229	11582
2012	10	1	16:10	6.3	2.4	2.4	4.1	64	0.09	8.08	-12.9	-10.5	111235	11582
2012	10	9	0:00	3.0	-2.2	-2.2	-1.6	-91	-0.26	5.85	-19.9	12.6	111285	11585
2012	10	9	6:00	2.8	-2.1	-2.0	3.7	-68	-0.25	5.78	-19.9	15.9	111288	11585
2012	10	13	18:37	4.8	3.4	3.4	3.3	81	0.21	6.71	11.9	-25.0	111318	11589
2012	10	13	20:00	4.8	3.5	3.5	2.7	92	0.21	6.72	11.9	-24.2	111319	11589
2012	10	15	3:00	5.5	1.5	1.4	2.9	10	0.08	6.54	11.9	-7.1	111326	11589
2012	10	15	18:15	4.9	1.1	1.1	3.5	20	0.07	6.52	11.9	1.4	111331	11589
2012	10	15	20:00	4.7	1.0	1.1	6.0	44	0.07	6.58	11.9	2.4	111333	11589
2012	10	15	22:55	4.6	1.0	1.0	8.2	48	0.06	6.52	11.9	4.0	111334	11589
2012	10	19	13:07	1.9	-0.8	-0.8	-3.6	-28	-0.19	4.17	14.2	-26.6	111364	11593
2012	10	19	18:53	2.0	-1.1	-1.1	1.7	-17	-0.25	4.42	14.2	-23.4	111365	11593
2012	10	20	12:04	1.9	-1.1	-1.0	-1.0	-42	-0.24	4.48	14.2	-13.9	111366	11593
2012	10	20	18:19	2.0	-1.2	-1.1	-3.8	-58	-0.26	4.46	14.2	-10.4	111367	11593

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	10	21	0:05	2.2	-1.3	-1.2	-0.5	-56	-0.26	4.42	14.2	-7.3	111368	11593
2012	10	21	6:30	2.2	-1.2	-1.1	0.4	-61	-0.25	4.32	14.2	-3.7	111369	11593
2012	10	21	18:30	2.1	-0.9	-0.9	-2.0	-53	-0.21	4.07	14.2	2.9	111371	11593
2012	10	25	11:05	6.8	5.3	5.3	-3.6	112	0.25	6.31	-12.8	-26.0	111391	11598
2012	10	25	14:15	6.9	4.8	4.8	-2.5	72	0.22	6.24	-12.8	-24.3	111392	11598
2012	10	25	16:40	6.6	4.6	4.6	-1.0	55	0.22	6.20	-12.8	-23.0	111393	11598
2012	10	25	19:50	6.7	4.2	4.2	3.9	64	0.20	6.39	-12.8	-21.2	111394	11598
2012	10	25	23:00	6.8	3.6	3.5	5.0	107	0.16	6.38	-12.9	-19.5	111395	11598
2012	10	27	1:00	6.5	0.1	0.1	9.8	94	0.01	6.80	-12.9	-5.2	111406	11598
2012	10	27	3:45	6.5	-0.8	-0.8	2.7	36	-0.03	6.88	-12.9	-3.6	111407	11598
2012	10	27	5:15	6.5	-0.7	-0.8	11.9	66	-0.03	7.01	-12.9	-2.8	111408	11598
2012	10	27	7:15	6.4	-1.2	-1.2	8.7	23	-0.05	7.00	-12.9	-1.7	111409	11598
2012	10	27	9:15	6.3	-1.2	-1.3	4.5	11	-0.06	6.99	-12.9	-0.6	111410	11598
2012	10	27	10:30	6.3	-1.3	-1.3	4.5	31	-0.06	6.90	-12.9	0.1	111411	11598
2012	10	27	12:30	6.2	-1.4	-1.5	8.9	59	-0.07	6.94	-12.9	1.2	111412	11598
2012	10	27	14:30	6.2	-1.4	-1.4	8.0	53	-0.06	7.02	-12.9	2.3	111413	11598
2012	10	27	16:10	6.0	-1.3	-1.3	8.6	40	-0.06	7.05	-12.9	3.2	111414	11598
2012	10	27	19:00	6.1	-1.7	-1.8	4.0	12	-0.08	6.99	-12.9	4.8	111415	11598
2012	10	27	21:00	5.9	-1.8	-1.8	-0.6	2	-0.09	6.99	-12.9	5.8	111416	11598
2012	10	27	23:40	5.8	-1.9	-1.9	-1.1	4	-0.09	6.92	-12.9	7.3	111417	11598
2012	10	28	1:40	5.8	-1.9	-1.9	1.5	1	-0.09	6.89	-12.9	8.4	111418	11598
2012	10	28	4:15	5.7	-2.0	-2.1	0.3	-22	-0.10	6.92	-12.9	9.8	111419	11598
2012	10	28	10:40	5.4	-2.1	-2.2	4.5	-13	-0.12	6.85	-12.9	13.4	111422	11598
2012	10	28	12:40	5.3	-2.2	-2.2	1.1	-38	-0.12	6.88	-12.9	14.5	111423	11598
2012	10	28	14:40	5.3	-2.2	-2.2	-0.6	-36	-0.12	6.84	-12.9	15.6	111424	11598
2012	10	28	16:40	5.2	-1.9	-2.0	3.7	-14	-0.11	6.85	-12.9	16.7	111425	11598
2012	10	28	19:30	4.9	-1.9	-1.9	3.9	-27	-0.11	6.82	-12.9	18.2	111426	11598
2012	10	28	21:30	4.9	-1.8	-1.8	5.4	-22	-0.11	6.87	-12.9	19.3	111427	11598
2012	10	28	23:20	4.8	-1.6	-1.7	-1.0	-45	-0.10	6.83	-12.9	20.4	111428	11598
2012	10	29	1:45	4.6	-1.5	-1.5	1.1	-25	-0.10	6.76	-12.9	21.7	111429	11598
2012	10	29	3:45	4.5	-1.4	-1.4	4.6	-9	-0.09	6.71	-12.9	22.8	111430	11598
2012	10	29	5:30	4.3	-1.2	-1.2	0.3	-25	-0.08	6.56	-12.9	23.7	111431	11598
2012	10	29	8:15	4.4	-1.1	-1.1	-0.4	-27	-0.07	6.64	-12.8	25.3	111432	11598

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	10	29	10:15	4.3	-0.7	-0.7	4.1	-10	-0.05	6.62	-12.9	26.4	111433	11598
2012	10	29	12:15	4.2	-0.6	-0.6	-1.6	-31	-0.05	6.59	-12.8	27.5	111434	11598
2012	10	29	14:15	4.1	-0.5	-0.5	1.7	-27	-0.04	6.67	-12.8	27.8	111435	11598
2012	11	2	6:15	1.0	-0.0	-0.0	1.8	9	-0.01	4.08	-18.0	-24.9	111465	11602
2012	11	2	16:50	0.9	-0.0	-0.0	0.7	11	-0.01	4.00	-18.0	-19.1	111468	11602
2012	11	2	19:20	0.9	0.0	-0.0	2.7	14	0.00	3.82	-18.0	-17.7	111469	11602
2012	11	3	14:55	0.8	-0.0	-0.0	1.6	12	-0.00	3.45	-20.2	-5.6	111471	11602
2012	11	3	17:00	0.8	-0.0	-0.0	1.9	9	-0.00	3.47	-20.2	-4.5	111472	11602
2012	11	3	23:10	0.9	-0.0	-0.0	2.3	8	-0.02	3.19	-20.2	-1.1	111474	11602
2012	11	4	5:20	0.9	0.0	0.0	1.4	9	0.01	3.10	-20.2	2.3	111475	11602
2012	11	9	2:22	0.5	0.1	0.1	1.5	12	0.10	3.27	-22.4	-27.1	111508	11608
2012	11	9	5:10	0.5	0.1	0.1	1.4	17	0.11	3.24	-22.4	-25.6	111509	11608
2012	11	9	6:47	0.6	0.1	0.1	1.8	24	0.11	3.06	-22.4	-24.7	111510	11608
2012	11	9	9:00	0.5	0.1	0.1	1.6	25	0.16	3.21	-22.4	-23.6	111511	11608
2012	11	9	10:05	0.6	0.1	0.1	2.5	25	0.11	3.09	-22.4	-23.0	111512	11608
2012	11	9	17:07	0.6	0.1	0.1	2.3	25	0.10	2.88	-22.4	-19.2	111513	11608
2012	11	10	4:40	0.5	0.1	0.1	3.4	27	0.13	2.75	-22.4	-12.9	111519	11608
2012	11	12	2:15	1.9	-0.4	-0.4	2.3	13	-0.09	4.77	11.7	-27.4	111537	11611
2012	11	12	4:00	2.7	0.7	0.7	7.7	118	0.10	5.39	11.7	-26.4	111538	11611
2012	11	12	7:10	2.4	0.1	0.1	6.2	80	0.03	4.70	11.7	-24.7	111539	11611
2012	11	12	8:45	2.3	0.2	0.1	6.8	86	0.04	4.61	11.7	-23.8	111540	11611
2012	11	12	10:30	2.3	0.1	0.1	6.2	58	0.02	4.63	11.7	-22.8	111541	11611
2012	11	12	12:15	3.2	1.0	0.9	13.8	199	0.13	4.82	11.7	-21.9	111542	11611
2012	11	14	13:16	2.4	0.9	0.8	6.2	140	0.17	4.16	-24.5	-28.4	111549	11613
2012	11	14	15:45	2.3	0.8	0.8	6.0	127	0.17	4.25	-24.5	-27.1	111550	11613
2012	11	15	7:30	2.1	0.8	0.8	6.1	88	0.16	4.57	-24.5	-18.7	111551	11613
2012	11	15	10:48	2.1	0.7	0.6	2.7	52	0.13	4.65	-24.5	-16.9	111552	11613
2012	11	15	12:15	2.1	0.7	0.7	2.4	48	0.14	4.75	-24.5	-16.1	111553	11613
2012	11	15	13:15	2.1	0.7	0.7	1.8	39	0.14	4.81	-24.5	-15.6	111554	11613
2012	11	15	14:10	2.1	0.7	0.6	3.2	49	0.13	4.78	-24.5	-15.1	111555	11613
2012	11	15	14:48	2.0	0.6	0.6	1.6	39	0.12	5.00	-24.5	-14.8	111556	11613
2012	11	15	16:15	2.1	0.7	0.6	4.5	59	0.13	4.82	-24.5	-14.0	111557	11613
2012	11	15	19:15	2.0	0.6	0.6	3.7	55	0.13	4.77	-24.5	-12.4	111558	11613

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	11	15	20:18	2.0	0.7	0.7	2.8	52	0.14	5.12	-24.5	-11.8	111559	11613
2012	11	15	21:15	2.1	0.8	0.8	4.5	58	0.15	5.01	-24.5	-11.3	111560	11613
2012	11	15	23:00	2.1	0.7	0.7	4.2	58	0.13	5.02	-24.5	-10.4	111561	11613
2012	11	16	6:39	2.1	0.6	0.6	3.2	39	0.11	4.98	-24.5	-6.2	111562	11613
2012	11	16	11:15	2.2	0.4	0.4	1.3	36	0.07	4.94	-24.5	-3.8	111563	11613
2012	11	16	13:00	2.3	0.3	0.3	2.7	29	0.05	4.89	-24.5	-2.9	111564	11613
2012	11	17	2:05	2.2	-0.1	-0.1	2.6	17	-0.01	4.69	-24.5	4.2	111565	11613
2012	11	17	7:00	2.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.5	3	-0.02	4.85	-24.5	6.8	111566	11613
2012	11	17	10:25	2.1	-0.1	-0.1	3.7	37	-0.02	4.77	-24.4	10.2	111567	11613
2012	11	17	13:30	2.0	-0.0	-0.1	1.4	36	-0.01	4.80	-24.4	11.8	111568	11613
2012	11	17	17:30	1.7	0.0	0.0	1.3	27	0.01	5.00	-24.3	13.0	111569	11613
2012	11	21	12:14	7.8	-0.3	-0.2	-4.6	-180	-0.02	4.79	7.0	-7.3	111605	11618
2012	11	22	0:51	8.7	1.9	1.8	23.2	157	0.08	5.62	7.0	-0.5	111606	11618
2012	11	22	15:30	9.1	3.4	3.3	7.3	173	0.12	6.30	7.0	7.8	111608	11618
2012	11	22	20:15	8.8	3.5	3.4	5.5	156	0.13	6.22	7.0	10.4	111609	11618
2012	11	23	1:05	8.4	2.1	2.0	12.0	114	0.08	6.38	7.0	13.1	111610	11618
2012	11	23	7:30	7.7	1.2	1.2	3.9	39	0.05	6.48	7.0	16.7	111611	11618
2012	11	23	12:11	6.0	0.6	0.6	9.4	26	0.03	6.68	7.0	19.1	111612	11618
2012	11	23	13:01	7.0	1.3	1.3	13.8	25	0.06	6.38	7.0	19.8	111613	11618
2012	11	23	19:22	6.5	1.4	1.4	12.0	104	0.07	6.49	7.0	23.3	111614	11618
2012	11	30	3:30	1.9	-0.4	-0.4	-1.9	-10	-0.08	5.77	14.0	-10.7	111631	11621
2012	11	30	5:20	1.9	-0.5	-0.5	1.6	-12	-0.08	5.65	14.0	-7.1	111632	11621
2012	12	3	7:00	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	3.7	0	-0.04	3.50	12.2	-5.3	111633	11625
2012	12	3	10:07	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	1.2	0	-0.03	3.59	12.2	-3.6	111634	11625
2012	12	3	13:00	1.7	-0.1	-0.1	-0.5	-13	-0.04	3.43	12.2	-2.0	111635	11625
2012	12	3	15:45	1.4	-0.1	-0.1	2.4	0	-0.04	3.65	12.2	-0.5	111636	11625
2012	12	3	18:52	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	3.6	-1	-0.04	3.35	12.2	1.2	111637	11625
2012	12	3	22:05	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	2.3	-6	-0.05	3.34	12.2	3.0	111638	11625
2012	12	4	1:06	1.5	-0.2	-0.1	1.5	-3	-0.06	3.40	12.2	4.7	111639	11625
2012	12	4	4:17	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	3.0	-7	-0.07	3.45	12.2	6.4	111640	11625
2012	12	20	2:05	2.4	1.1	1.0	5.2	109	0.17	5.26	-7.0	-13.3	111715	11633
2012	12	20	3:55	2.4	1.0	0.9	3.9	112	0.16	5.23	-7.0	-12.3	111716	11633
2012	12	20	15:16	2.4	0.8	0.8	5.8	88	0.14	4.87	-7.5	-4.7	111717	11633

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2012	12	21	2:01	2.6	1.4	1.3	7.0	109	0.22	4.63	-7.5	1.3	111720	11633
2012	12	22	2:26	2.5	1.4	1.4	6.7	136	0.26	4.37	-7.5	14.8	111721	11633
2012	12	22	4:15	2.5	1.5	1.4	8.9	124	0.27	4.41	-7.5	15.8	111722	11633
2012	12	22	10:49	2.5	1.2	1.2	3.7	93	0.24	4.24	-7.5	17.8	111723	11633
2012	12	22	19:12	1.1	0.0	0.0	-3.8	-3	0.01	3.45	-7.5	22.4	111725	11633
2012	12	23	0:00	2.9	1.8	1.6	7.5	221	0.29	4.29	-7.5	25.1	111726	11633
2012	12	26	1:34	4.4	-2.9	-2.9	-10.4	-180	-0.32	4.07	10.2	16.6	111740	11635
2012	12	26	8:05	4.0	-2.6	-2.5	-11.6	-205	-0.34	3.80	10.2	20.2	111742	11635
2012	12	31	19:52	0.8	0.1	0.1	2.2	30	0.07	2.85	12.6	13.4	111757	11636
2013	1	1	0:29	0.9	0.1	0.1	-0.2	21	0.06	2.93	12.6	15.9	111758	11636
2013	1	3	9:41	1.2	0.3	0.2	1.5	28	0.12	3.54	-15.2	-5.7	111759	11645
2013	1	4	9:00	1.1	0.4	0.4	-0.9	17	0.22	3.43	-15.2	7.0	111765	11645
2013	1	4	14:01	1.1	0.4	0.3	2.3	43	0.19	3.32	-15.2	9.9	111767	11645
2013	1	4	19:00	1.1	0.3	0.3	3.4	36	0.15	3.34	-15.2	12.7	111768	11645
2013	1	4	23:48	1.1	0.3	0.3	2.0	48	0.16	3.38	-15.2	15.3	111769	11645
2013	1	5	4:45	1.1	0.3	0.3	3.6	36	0.15	3.38	-15.2	18.0	111770	11645
2013	1	5	9:19	0.9	0.2	0.2	1.5	20	0.14	3.53	-15.2	20.5	111771	11645
2013	1	12	0:40	3.1	-0.6	-0.6	7.2	-45	-0.07	5.43	20.0	-2.2	111785	11652
2013	1	12	7:08	2.9	-0.3	-0.3	3.1	-53	-0.04	5.35	20.0	1.3	111786	11652
2013	1	12	21:57	6.7	2.2	2.3	-7.5	-76	0.09	7.27	7.7	-22.9	111792	11654
2013	1	13	3:36	6.8	3.3	3.4	-2.6	-1	0.13	7.26	7.7	-19.8	111794	11654
2013	1	15	7:30	5.2	1.7	1.8	10.2	0	0.11	5.93	7.7	9.1	111808	11654
2013	2	2	7:02	3.2	-0.1	-0.1	3.1	15	-0.01	6.49	10.2	-20.6	111869	11665
2013	2	9	15:11	3.3	-0.1	-0.1	2.2	4	-0.01	6.23	16.7	-4.8	111893	11670
2013	2	9	20:00	3.5	-0.0	0.0	3.5	-8	-0.00	6.17	16.7	-2.2	111894	11670
2013	2	10	1:00	3.6	0.2	0.2	3.8	22	0.02	6.07	16.7	0.6	111895	11670
2013	2	10	9:00	3.8	0.1	0.1	1.7	4	0.00	6.24	16.7	5.0	111896	11670
2013	2	10	14:30	3.9	-0.1	-0.1	0.5	-8	-0.01	6.22	16.7	8.0	111897	11670
2013	2	10	19:00	4.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.9	0	-0.01	6.07	16.7	10.5	111898	11670
2013	2	12	11:43	3.1	0.4	0.4	1.6	24	0.05	5.31	16.6	18.3	111900	11670
2013	2	12	23:20	2.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	17	0.05	5.04	16.4	24.6	111908	11670
2013	2	18	11:05	1.9	0.3	0.3	1.0	22	0.07	4.64	13.1	24.5	111915	11671
2013	2	18	13:05	1.9	0.3	0.3	2.0	27	0.08	4.58	13.1	25.6	111916	11671

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	2	18	15:55	1.9	0.3	0.3	1.0	33	0.08	4.31	13.1	27.2	111917	11671
2013	2	19	11:15	1.0	0.0	0.0	3.4	12	0.00	4.88	11.6	0.1	111919	11675
2013	2	19	13:30	1.0	-0.0	-0.0	2.2	5	-0.01	4.97	11.7	1.4	111920	11675
2013	2	19	16:30	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.7	-3	-0.03	4.95	11.7	3.0	111921	11675
2013	2	19	19:40	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	-1.5	-11	-0.02	4.76	11.7	4.8	111922	11675
2013	2	19	23:00	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.4	-6	-0.05	4.88	11.7	6.6	111923	11675
2013	2	20	2:00	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.0	-2	-0.02	4.80	11.7	8.3	111924	11675
2013	3	4	4:30	2.5	-0.3	-0.3	4.9	51	-0.05	4.66	-16.8	-28.6	111975	11683
2013	3	4	7:40	2.5	-0.3	-0.3	5.9	58	-0.05	4.70	-16.8	-26.9	111976	11683
2013	3	4	18:25	2.4	-0.4	-0.4	4.6	29	-0.07	4.71	-16.8	-21.0	111979	11683
2013	3	4	21:30	2.4	-0.6	-0.6	7.2	43	-0.10	4.79	-16.8	-19.3	111980	11683
2013	3	5	0:35	2.4	-0.5	-0.5	8.5	57	-0.09	4.83	-16.8	-17.6	111981	11683
2013	3	5	3:30	2.2	-0.5	-0.5	9.4	62	-0.09	4.67	-16.8	-16.1	111982	11683
2013	3	5	6:40	2.2	-0.5	-0.5	3.9	37	-0.10	4.70	-16.8	-14.3	111983	11683
2013	3	5	20:21	1.9	-0.6	-0.6	1.3	21	-0.14	4.63	-16.8	-4.2	111985	11683
2013	3	5	23:30	1.8	-0.6	-0.6	1.3	15	-0.15	4.50	-16.8	-2.4	111986	11683
2013	4	2	18:18	1.0	-0.1	-0.0	-1.3	-20	-0.04	3.11	10.4	-7.6	112129	11708
2013	4	2	23:15	1.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.1	-22	-0.10	3.12	10.4	-4.8	112130	11708
2013	4	3	3:15	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	-5.4	-50	-0.13	3.05	10.4	-2.6	112131	11708
2013	4	3	21:47	7.7	4.6	4.6	1.3	59	0.13	9.26	-19.4	-29.1	112134	11711
2013	4	4	2:37	7.5	4.7	4.7	3.0	67	0.14	9.27	-19.4	-26.5	112135	11711
2013	4	4	6:09	7.8	5.4	5.3	4.2	97	0.15	9.35	-19.4	-24.6	112136	11711
2013	4	4	9:09	7.7	5.5	5.5	6.3	120	0.15	9.26	-19.4	-23.0	112137	11711
2013	4	4	15:50	7.7	4.1	4.1	2.3	52	0.12	9.21	-18.4	-17.7	112139	11711
2013	4	4	18:15	7.7	4.0	4.0	-0.5	45	0.11	9.28	-18.4	-16.6	112140	11711
2013	4	4	22:00	7.7	3.6	3.6	0.5	37	0.10	9.30	-18.4	-14.5	112141	11711
2013	4	5	0:00	7.7	3.4	3.3	-1.5	32	0.09	9.34	-18.4	-13.4	112142	11711
2013	4	5	3:00	7.7	3.5	3.5	-1.4	35	0.10	9.32	-18.4	-11.8	112143	11711
2013	4	5	6:27	7.7	3.7	3.7	-1.5	30	0.10	9.37	-18.4	-9.9	112144	11711
2013	4	5	9:30	7.8	3.7	3.7	-3.0	32	0.10	9.41	-18.4	-8.3	112145	11711
2013	4	5	13:00	7.4	3.7	3.7	0.2	23	0.11	9.33	-18.4	-6.4	112146	11711
2013	4	5	18:15	7.6	3.8	3.7	-2.8	32	0.10	9.33	-18.4	-3.5	112147	11711
2013	4	6	0:30	7.5	3.5	3.6	-0.0	29	0.10	9.35	-18.4	-0.1	112148	11711

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	4	6	6:35	7.4	3.6	3.6	0.9	39	0.10	9.24	-18.4	3.2	112149	11711
2013	4	11	14:14	5.3	-4.3	-4.3	-3.9	-162	-0.29	5.55	8.6	-5.7	112155	11714
2013	4	11	18:25	7.2	-0.1	-0.0	9.2	24	-0.00	7.24	21.0	28.0	112156	11718
2013	4	13	16:25	4.2	0.5	0.5	-0.6	48	0.04	6.03	-20.3	1.4	112166	11721
2013	5	1	6:15	7.1	4.8	4.7	10.1	282	0.30	4.49	8.1	6.9	112195	11731
2013	5	2	1:31	4.9	2.2	2.2	7.3	80	0.19	4.58	8.1	17.6	112196	11731
2013	5	2	8:02	4.8	2.3	2.3	2.3	50	0.21	4.50	8.1	21.2	112197	11731
2013	5	7	11:15	2.2	0.6	0.6	4.7	42	0.13	4.30	11.1	-23.9	112224	11738
2013	5	7	12:53	2.1	0.6	0.6	1.3	25	0.13	4.36	11.1	-23.0	112225	11738
2013	5	7	14:45	2.1	0.5	0.5	4.6	33	0.10	4.34	11.1	-22.0	112226	11738
2013	5	7	16:30	2.0	0.5	0.5	4.6	26	0.12	4.32	11.1	-21.0	112227	11738
2013	5	7	23:00	2.2	0.5	0.5	3.6	34	0.10	4.26	11.1	-17.4	112228	11738
2013	5	8	3:40	2.2	0.5	0.4	3.2	34	0.09	4.34	11.1	-14.8	112229	11738
2013	5	8	10:14	2.2	0.4	0.4	3.2	37	0.08	4.33	11.1	-11.2	112230	11738
2013	5	8	11:53	2.1	0.4	0.4	4.2	42	0.09	4.32	11.1	-10.3	112231	11738
2013	5	8	22:00	2.1	0.4	0.4	2.2	41	0.09	4.29	11.1	-4.7	112232	11738
2013	5	9	1:01	2.1	0.3	0.3	1.9	35	0.08	4.29	11.1	-3.0	112233	11738
2013	5	9	7:35	2.1	0.2	0.2	2.5	27	0.05	4.28	11.1	0.6	112234	11738
2013	5	9	9:13	2.1	0.3	0.2	7.3	40	0.06	4.27	11.1	1.5	112235	11738
2013	5	9	10:52	2.0	0.2	0.2	4.1	29	0.05	4.29	11.1	2.5	112236	11738
2013	5	9	12:30	2.1	0.2	0.2	6.8	37	0.05	4.22	11.1	3.4	112237	11738
2013	5	9	14:15	2.0	0.2	0.2	6.6	39	0.05	4.18	11.1	4.3	112238	11738
2013	5	9	16:06	2.1	0.2	0.2	5.9	48	0.04	4.10	11.1	5.3	112239	11738
2013	5	10	6:38	2.1	0.5	0.5	7.5	65	0.13	3.77	11.1	13.4	112240	11738
2013	5	10	8:12	2.1	0.5	0.5	9.0	81	0.14	3.70	11.1	14.3	112241	11738
2013	5	10	9:51	2.0	0.5	0.5	7.3	89	0.14	3.61	11.1	15.2	112242	11738
2013	5	10	11:29	2.0	0.5	0.5	8.1	87	0.14	3.54	11.1	16.1	112243	11738
2013	5	10	13:08	1.9	0.4	0.4	8.3	78	0.12	3.46	11.1	17.0	112244	11738
2013	5	10	14:55	1.8	0.4	0.3	7.6	73	0.11	3.52	11.1	18.0	112245	11738
2013	6	13	11:15	1.6	-0.0	-0.0	2.7	9	-0.01	4.15	-13.2	25.2	112390	11768
2013	6	17	0:35	2.6	0.4	0.4	5.0	67	0.05	5.18	-23.1	-30.9	112408	11772
2013	6	17	3:52	2.4	0.3	0.3	-1.5	0	0.04	5.32	-23.1	-29.1	112409	11772
2013	6	17	8:47	2.5	0.3	0.2	6.8	27	0.04	5.39	-23.1	-26.5	112410	11772

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	6	17	12:04	2.7	0.3	0.3	6.3	42	0.05	5.28	-23.1	-24.7	112411	11772
2013	6	17	15:32	2.6	0.2	0.2	0.9	3	0.03	5.39	-23.1	-22.8	112412	11772
2013	6	17	18:47	2.7	0.2	0.3	3.5	8	0.03	5.52	-23.1	-18.5	112413	11772
2013	6	17	22:00	2.8	0.4	0.4	4.5	25	0.05	5.67	-23.1	-16.8	112414	11772
2013	6	18	1:12	2.9	0.6	0.6	4.5	45	0.07	5.55	-23.1	-15.0	112415	11772
2013	6	18	4:29	3.0	0.5	0.4	7.3	54	0.05	5.71	-23.1	-13.3	112416	11772
2013	6	18	7:46	3.0	0.4	0.3	4.6	49	0.04	5.81	-23.1	-11.5	112417	11772
2013	6	29	7:59	1.9	1.2	1.2	8.1	96	0.29	4.30	-19.0	3.0	112503	11778
2013	7	7	9:39	10.1	5.6	5.5	11.4	259	0.17	6.56	-12.1	-7.8	112544	11785
2013	7	7	11:20	9.5	9.6	9.5	14.8	271	0.32	6.22	-12.1	-7.3	112545	11785
2013	7	7	12:58	11.0	7.5	7.5	6.8	157	0.20	6.74	-12.1	-6.3	112546	11785
2013	7	9	12:31	7.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	-7	0.08	6.28	-13.2	24.0	112555	11785
2013	7	9	22:28	7.0	1.5	1.6	-0.1	-60	0.07	6.25	-13.1	28.5	112559	11785
2013	7	19	18:51	3.8	-0.3	-0.3	4.5	39	-0.02	6.25	18.9	-14.4	112599	11793
2013	7	19	23:33	3.5	-0.3	-0.3	2.1	41	-0.02	6.26	18.9	-11.8	112600	11793
2013	7	20	3:38	1.0	0.3	0.3	3.5	56	0.16	4.02	18.9	-10.4	112601	11793
2013	7	20	6:24	3.4	-0.3	-0.3	5.7	32	-0.03	5.91	18.9	-8.1	112602	11793
2013	7	20	18:21	2.8	0.2	0.2	4.9	48	0.02	6.23	19.4	1.8	112603	11793
2013	7	20	19:15	3.1	0.4	0.4	6.1	85	0.05	5.84	19.4	2.5	112604	11793
2013	7	20	21:04	3.2	0.5	0.4	5.7	74	0.05	5.69	19.4	3.5	112605	11793
2013	7	21	0:11	3.2	0.4	0.4	0.6	11	0.04	5.58	19.4	5.0	112606	11793
2013	7	21	1:50	3.1	0.3	0.4	5.3	0	0.04	5.57	19.4	5.9	112607	11793
2013	7	21	13:18	2.9	0.5	0.4	6.6	91	0.06	5.35	19.4	12.4	112609	11793
2013	7	22	2:26	2.5	0.1	0.1	7.5	54	0.01	5.60	19.4	19.6	112611	11793
2013	7	23	18:16	1.4	0.4	0.4	4.2	2	0.13	3.88	-9.9	-1.9	112617	11800
2013	7	24	23:22	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.9	-2	-0.03	4.70	-9.9	14.3	112647	11800
2013	7	25	4:30	1.4	-0.1	-0.1	1.7	5	-0.04	5.01	-9.9	17.0	112649	11800
2013	7	25	10:52	1.9	-0.3	-0.2	3.8	-14	-0.06	4.85	-9.3	23.2	112650	11800
2013	7	25	12:29	1.7	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-31	-0.08	4.94	-9.3	24.0	112651	11800
2013	7	25	14:08	1.9	-0.5	-0.5	4.3	-15	-0.11	5.02	-9.3	25.0	112652	11800
2013	8	2	1:00	2.6	0.0	0.0	0.9	-4	0.00	5.64	-17.9	3.9	112641	11806
2013	8	2	5:54	2.8	0.2	0.2	4.9	9	0.03	5.80	-17.9	6.6	112642	11806
2013	8	2	10:49	3.1	0.3	0.3	2.9	26	0.03	5.81	-17.9	9.2	112643	11806

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	8	2	12:27	3.2	0.3	0.3	1.4	16	0.03	5.89	-17.9	10.1	112644	11806
2013	8	2	20:50	3.0	0.1	0.1	5.4	41	0.02	5.56	-17.9	14.7	112645	11806
2013	8	3	1:35	3.0	0.4	0.4	0.6	15	0.04	6.08	-17.9	17.3	112657	11806
2013	8	4	20:35	2.1	0.6	0.6	2.9	43	0.12	4.81	10.0	-19.8	112662	11809
2013	8	8	16:28	1.1	0.0	-0.0	-0.8	0	0.00	3.74	12.8	27.8	112672	11809
2013	8	8	18:06	1.1	0.0	-0.0	0.1	1	0.00	3.68	12.8	28.8	112673	11809
2013	8	17	10:17	4.3	3.0	2.7	11.8	351	0.24	5.70	-6.4	24.3	112681	11818
2013	8	20	22:05	2.8	1.3	1.3	8.5	91	0.18	5.20	-6.3	-6.0	112695	11823
2013	8	21	22:04	2.1	1.1	1.1	4.1	49	0.19	5.59	-7.9	7.1	112716	11823
2013	8	21	23:05	2.1	1.1	1.1	3.3	64	0.19	5.60	-7.9	7.7	112717	11823
2013	8	22	0:06	2.1	1.1	1.1	1.2	51	0.19	5.58	-7.9	8.2	112718	11823
2013	8	22	20:05	1.8	0.3	0.3	2.1	18	0.07	5.17	-18.7	-22.3	112719	11827
2013	8	23	1:05	1.8	0.2	0.2	2.2	28	0.05	4.99	-18.7	-19.5	112723	11827
2013	8	23	11:04	1.6	0.1	0.1	3.8	22	0.02	5.09	-18.7	-14.1	112724	11827
2013	8	23	20:59	1.4	0.2	0.2	5.6	28	0.05	5.22	-18.7	-8.7	112725	11827
2013	8	24	9:41	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	-1.6	-2	-0.03	4.11	16.0	-14.2	112729	11828
2013	8	24	11:11	0.9	-0.0	-0.0	1.9	10	-0.01	4.03	16.0	-13.4	112730	11828
2013	8	24	12:41	0.9	-0.0	-0.1	0.5	5	-0.02	4.09	16.0	-12.5	112731	11828
2013	8	24	14:40	0.9	-0.1	-0.1	1.0	1	-0.04	4.09	16.0	-11.4	112732	11828
2013	8	24	16:30	0.9	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-1	-0.04	4.03	16.0	-10.4	112733	11828
2013	8	25	8:30	0.9	-0.2	-0.2	0.1	5	-0.09	4.08	16.0	-1.6	112738	11828
2013	8	25	13:00	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	1.3	-2	-0.04	4.22	16.0	0.8	112741	11828
2013	8	25	14:20	1.1	-0.1	-0.1	-1.4	-7	-0.05	4.16	16.0	1.6	112742	11828
2013	8	28	23:35	1.4	0.1	0.1	2.0	25	0.05	4.19	11.9	-28.1	112754	11836
2013	9	15	17:56	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	-0.2	7	-0.00	3.42	-7.0	-21.5	112935	11841
2013	9	15	22:30	0.6	0.0	0.0	-0.1	6	0.02	3.44	-7.0	-19.0	112936	11841
2013	9	16	6:15	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.2	16	0.03	3.43	-7.0	-14.7	112942	11841
2013	9	19	16:52	1.3	0.6	0.6	3.9	56	0.23	4.05	-0.3	15.9	113001	11843
2013	9	19	18:30	1.2	0.6	0.5	4.2	47	0.22	4.01	-0.3	16.8	113002	11843
2013	9	25	6:33	2.7	1.1	0.9	4.1	239	0.23	3.43	8.7	-6.8	113030	11850
2013	9	26	8:06	2.6	0.9	0.8	-0.1	109	0.17	4.26	8.7	7.4	113034	11850
2013	9	26	10:51	1.9	-0.2	-0.2	5.8	29	-0.05	4.85	8.7	11.5	113035	11850
2013	9	26	11:16	1.9	-0.2	-0.2	3.0	14	-0.05	4.84	8.7	11.7	113036	11850

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	9	27	0:01	1.8	-0.2	-0.2	1.8	5	-0.05	4.18	8.7	18.8	113038	11850
2013	9	27	8:00	1.9	-0.0	-0.0	-1.2	15	-0.00	4.04	8.7	23.2	113039	11850
2013	9	27	8:30	1.9	-0.0	-0.1	1.3	8	-0.01	4.01	8.7	23.5	113040	11850
2013	9	27	9:00	1.9	0.1	0.0	0.6	20	0.02	4.02	8.7	23.8	113041	11850
2013	9	27	9:30	1.9	0.1	0.1	2.9	26	0.03	4.04	8.7	24.1	113042	11850
2013	9	27	10:00	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	1.3	1	-0.03	3.97	8.7	24.3	113043	11850
2013	9	27	10:30	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	-1.2	-3	-0.03	3.96	8.7	24.6	113044	11850
2013	9	27	11:00	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	2.4	-2	-0.04	3.90	8.7	24.9	113045	11850
2013	10	2	13:06	3.0	0.2	0.1	7.5	27	0.02	4.97	-13.8	3.1	113059	11855
2013	10	2	16:00	3.1	0.2	0.2	7.0	35	0.02	4.87	-13.8	4.7	113060	11855
2013	10	2	19:15	2.9	0.1	0.1	3.5	11	0.02	4.80	-13.8	6.4	113061	11855
2013	10	2	21:00	2.8	0.2	0.2	0.2	16	0.03	4.71	-13.8	7.4	113062	11855
2013	10	3	1:30	2.6	0.2	0.2	3.6	18	0.03	4.64	-13.8	9.9	113063	11855
2013	10	3	5:00	2.5	0.4	0.4	5.3	8	0.07	4.56	-13.8	11.8	113064	11855
2013	10	7	16:21	1.6	0.2	0.1	2.3	58	0.04	4.42	6.9	-13.2	113081	11856
2013	10	7	21:15	1.7	0.4	0.4	-1.1	37	0.11	4.58	6.9	-10.4	113082	11856
2013	10	8	11:38	1.8	0.4	0.4	8.4	136	0.15	3.10	9.1	2.5	113084	11856
2013	10	8	13:38	1.8	0.5	0.4	5.3	111	0.16	3.24	9.1	3.6	113085	11856
2013	10	9	5:55	1.8	0.6	0.6	2.5	87	0.19	3.60	9.1	12.6	113086	11856
2013	10	9	9:50	1.8	0.6	0.5	5.0	93	0.17	3.62	9.1	14.8	113087	11856
2013	10	10	19:16	7.1	-3.0	-3.0	-4.9	-151	-0.15	5.45	-13.1	-26.1	113096	11861
2013	10	11	6:34	9.1	-3.5	-3.3	-2.0	-239	-0.14	5.59	-13.1	-19.9	113098	11861
2013	10	12	10:19	8.5	-0.8	-0.7	3.8	-40	-0.03	6.18	-9.0	-3.4	113101	11861
2013	10	21	18:13	5.8	-2.8	-2.6	-3.5	-232	-0.22	4.41	6.3	-24.5	113125	11875
2013	10	22	0:20	4.0	-1.2	-1.1	0.4	-136	-0.18	3.45	6.3	-21.1	113131	11875
2013	10	22	18:32	7.3	-1.4	-1.5	8.1	34	-0.10	3.96	6.3	-11.0	113132	11875
2013	10	23	6:18	8.9	-3.6	-3.8	-0.2	-38	-0.19	4.22	6.3	-4.5	113133	11875
2013	10	24	6:00	9.0	0.7	0.6	9.0	93	0.03	4.85	6.3	11.2	113155	11875
2013	10	24	10:34	8.9	-0.2	-0.3	1.8	36	-0.01	4.76	6.3	13.8	113156	11875
2013	10	29	0:00	4.6	-3.0	-2.8	-10.8	-254	-0.26	4.89	-9.4	-25.8	113173	11882
2013	10	29	15:30	6.2	-1.8	-1.8	-0.7	-91	-0.09	6.28	-10.0	-13.9	113175	11882
2013	10	29	18:13	6.0	-1.5	-1.4	-2.2	-77	-0.08	6.26	-10.0	-12.4	113176	11882
2013	10	29	21:00	6.0	-1.2	-1.1	2.5	-75	-0.06	6.31	-10.0	-10.9	113177	11882

Table 4 continued

Table 4 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	10	29	23:00	6.1	-1.3	-1.2	-1.0	-68	-0.07	6.33	-10.0	-9.8	113178	11882
2013	10	30	2:00	6.0	-1.4	-1.3	3.5	-71	-0.07	6.40	-10.0	-8.1	113179	11882
2013	10	30	5:00	6.0	-1.1	-1.1	-1.3	-43	-0.06	6.41	-10.0	-6.5	113180	11882
2013	10	30	8:00	6.0	-1.0	-0.9	-3.1	-45	-0.05	6.37	-10.0	-4.8	113181	11882
2013	10	30	10:00	6.0	-1.0	-1.0	-2.5	-22	-0.05	6.36	-10.0	-3.7	113182	11882
2013	10	30	12:29	5.8	-0.8	-0.8	2.4	13	-0.04	6.41	-10.0	-2.3	113183	11882
2013	10	30	15:00	5.6	-0.9	-0.9	-0.2	-12	-0.05	6.39	-10.0	-0.9	113184	11882
2013	10	30	23:15	5.3	-0.8	-0.8	2.5	4	-0.05	6.37	-10.0	3.6	113186	11882
2013	11	1	9:30	6.7	0.5	0.3	21.5	288	0.03	5.21	-14.6	-9.6	113188	11884
2013	11	1	15:00	6.6	0.8	0.6	26.0	311	0.04	5.21	-14.6	-6.5	113189	11884
2013	11	1	21:30	6.7	1.5	1.3	24.5	321	0.08	5.26	-14.6	-3.0	113190	11884
2013	11	2	0:10	6.6	0.7	0.6	24.1	297	0.04	5.26	-14.6	-1.5	113191	11884
2013	11	2	3:30	6.5	1.2	1.1	19.8	264	0.07	5.36	-14.6	0.3	113192	11884
2013	11	2	9:45	4.4	0.2	0.1	13.2	151	0.02	4.99	-13.3	3.7	113193	11884
2013	11	2	11:45	4.3	0.1	-0.0	8.8	133	0.01	4.99	-13.3	4.8	113194	11884
2013	11	2	13:45	4.2	0.0	-0.1	8.6	121	0.00	5.03	-13.3	5.9	113195	11884
2013	11	7	9:41	8.1	-1.3	-1.4	6.1	17	-0.04	7.44	-12.2	-21.0	113196	11890
2013	11	7	11:10	10.9	-2.5	-2.8	21.2	308	-0.08	5.60	-12.2	-20.2	113197	11890
2013	11	7	15:00	10.5	-5.3	-5.5	16.9	251	-0.16	6.52	-12.2	-18.1	113198	11890
2013	11	7	16:45	10.3	-3.2	-3.2	1.6	72	-0.08	7.33	-12.2	-17.1	113199	11890
2013	11	7	21:40	9.7	-2.5	-2.5	9.8	-5	-0.07	7.53	-12.2	-14.4	113200	11890
2013	11	8	2:10	9.2	-1.7	-1.7	6.2	-28	-0.05	7.73	-12.2	-11.9	113202	11890
2013	11	8	11:30	8.3	0.3	0.3	7.2	36	0.01	7.78	-12.2	-6.8	113203	11890
2013	11	8	19:00	8.4	0.3	0.3	12.0	56	0.01	7.23	-12.2	-2.6	113204	11890
2013	11	9	7:40	7.6	1.1	1.1	3.1	-9	0.04	7.58	-12.2	4.4	113205	11890
2013	11	10	3:20	6.1	-1.8	-2.0	12.5	260	-0.11	5.45	-12.8	12.8	113210	11890
2013	11	10	8:30	5.3	1.7	1.3	8.0	410	0.12	5.24	-12.8	15.6	113211	11890
2013	11	10	18:30	4.6	1.1	0.8	11.4	338	0.10	4.64	-12.8	21.1	113212	11890